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**Analysis of future grid tariff design:
Economic effects and possible peak load
reduction at the low voltage grid level**

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Sworn declaration

I hereby declare that I prepared this work independently and without help from third parties, that I did not use sources other than the ones referenced and that I have indicated passages taken from those sources.

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Wels, September 2025

Abstract

In Austria, grid-tariff reform is at the intersection of affordability, fairness, and dependability, making household bills and low-voltage (LV) grid peaks a pressing issue. Previous studies frequently examine a single tariff, a specific user group, or a single technology in isolation; this thesis evaluates numerous tariff designs across heterogeneous households within a single framework and compares baseline and stress-test adoption. The goal is to determine how volumetric, yearly-peak, and monthly-peak grid tariffs affect household electricity expenditures and LV peak metrics across different flexibility classes and portfolios of distributed generation and flexible household technology. Using 15-min data for 60 Austrian households, the models were solved with linear optimization in IESopt. The yearly-peak tariff charges the annual maximum 15-minute import; the monthly-peak tariff adds charges to each month's maximum; and for comparability, the stated peak metric is the average of monthly maxima. Peak-based tariffs lower total costs by 7.2-7.3% (baseline) and 13.6-13.7% (stress-test), with further reductions in grid-tariff charges (26.6-26.9% and 49.8-51.3%). LV peaks decline by 26.7% and 49.8%, with the highest gains occurring in particularly very flexible homes with battery storage. Yearly and monthly peak designs work similarly. The findings support peak-oriented grid pricing for demand control while also suggesting the necessity for periodic tariff recalibration in Austria to ensure distribution system operators (DSOs) income adequacy.

Kurzfassung

In Österreich liegt die Reform der Netzentgelte an der Schnittstelle von Bezahlbarkeit, Fairness und Zuverlässigkeit; damit rücken Haushaltsrechnungen und Spitzen im Niederspannungsnetz (NS) in den Fokus. Bisherige Studien betrachten häufig nur ein einzelnes Entgeltregime, eine spezifische Nutzergruppe oder eine Technologie isoliert; diese Studie bewertet mehrere Netzentgeltgestaltungen über heterogene Haushalte innerhalb eines einheitlichen Rahmens und vergleicht Ausgangs- und Stresstest-Annahmen. Ziel ist es zu bestimmen, wie volumetrische, jahresbezogene Spitzen- und monatsbezogene Spitzen-Netzentgelte die Stromausgaben der Haushalte und NS-Spitzenkennzahlen über verschiedene Flexibilitätsklassen und Portfolios verteilter Erzeugung und flexibler Haushaltstechnologien beeinflussen. Auf Basis von 15-minütigen Daten von 60 österreichischen Haushalten wurden die Modelle mit linearer Optimierung in IESopt gelöst. Das Jahres-Spitzenentgelt bemisst sich am jährlichen maximalen 15-Minuten-Netzbezug; das Monats-Spitzenentgelt erhebt Entgelte auf die monatlichen Maxima; zur Vergleichbarkeit wird als Spitzenkennzahl der Durchschnitt der monatlichen Maxima berücksichtigt. Spitzenorientierte Entgelte senken die Gesamtkosten um 7,2–7,3% (Ausgangsszenario) bzw. 13,6–13,7% (Stresstest) und reduzieren die Netzentgeltkosten noch deutlicher (26,6–26,9% bzw. 49,8–51,3%). NS-Spitzen gehen um 26,7% bzw. 49,8% zurück; die größten Effekte zeigen insbesondere sehr flexible Haushalte mit Batteriespeicher. Jahres- und Monats-Spitzenentgelte wirken ähnlich. Die Ergebnisse sprechen für spitzenorientierte Netzentgelte zur Laststeuerung und deuten zugleich auf die Notwendigkeit einer periodischen Tarifierung in Österreich hin, um die Erlösdeckung der Verteilnetzbetreiber (DSOs) sicherzustellen.

Contents

Acknowledgements	II
Sworn declaration	III
Abstract	IV
Kurzfassung	V
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 Background	1
1.3 Problem statement	1
1.4 Research gap	2
1.5 Research question and objectives	2
1.6 Method overview	2
1.7 Scope and assumptions	3
1.8 Structure of the thesis	3
2 State-of-the-art technology	4
2.1 Legal and institutional framework shaping the electricity grid . . .	4
2.2 Current grid tariff model in Austria	6
2.3 Related literature	8
2.3.1 Tariff design evolution: Volumetric to capacity-based structures . .	8
2.3.2 Household technology flexibility and demand response (DR) effec-	
tiveness	9
2.3.3 Economic distribution effects and household heterogeneity	11
2.3.4 DSO economic impacts and regulatory framework	12
2.3.5 Research gaps and contribution	13
3 Methodology	15
3.1 Description of households	15
3.2 Grid tariffs	19
3.2.1 Volumetric grid tariff	19
3.2.2 Yearly peak grid tariff	20
3.2.3 Monthly peak grid tariff	20
3.3 Total costs	21
	VI

3.4	Optimization tool	22
3.5	Optimization model	24
3.6	Scenario analysis	31
3.7	Limitations of the model	32
4	Results and discussion	33
4.1	Load profile analysis	34
4.1.1	Heat map for quarter-hourly electricity grid consumption values . .	34
4.1.2	Representative profiles by technology combinations	43
4.2	Comparative analysis of scenario–tariff combinations	60
4.2.1	Composition of total annual energy costs in all households	61
4.2.2	Total annual electricity expenditures by cost component	63
4.2.3	Average household electricity cost, grid tariff charges, and peak load contribution	65
4.2.4	Relative change in key metrics compared to the volumetric grid tariff baseline	67
4.3	Detailed results by household flexibility category	69
4.3.1	Results by grid tariff type	69
4.3.2	Results by technology combinations	78
4.4	Key findings summary	82
4.5	Integrated discussion and insights	84
4.5.1	Interpretation of key findings	84
4.5.2	Implications for key stakeholders	85
4.5.3	Limitations and future research	87
5	Conclusion	89
6	List of figures	92
7	List of tables	94
8	Bibliography	95
9	Appendix	99

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Electrification of heating and mobility concentrates household demand into short intervals, making coincident peaks more salient for planning and for what households pay. Grid tariffs therefore become a decisive lever: they allocate network costs, shape consumer incentives, and condition how distribution system operators recover expenditures. In Austria, the reform of grid tariffs is at the intersection of affordability, fairness, and reliability, so understanding how design choices influence household bills and peak demand is timely and consequential.

1.2 Background

Historically, grid tariff structures rely on volumetric charges that inadequately incentivize peak reduction, whereas peak-aligned components target the drivers of capacity needs. At the same time, household portfolios of distributed generation and flexible household technologies, such as photovoltaic systems, storage, heat pumps, and electric vehicles, expand the potential for demand shifting and on-site balancing. Previous studies show that responses to grid tariffs vary with technology availability, automation, and usage patterns, yet Austria-specific, household-granular comparisons across alternative grid tariff structures and technology combinations remain limited, particularly when adoption levels change and outcomes are compared holding all other parameters constant, so differences reflect grid tariff design alone.

1.3 Problem statement

Policy and regulatory discussions require clear quantitative evidence on how different grid tariff designs affect household costs and peak demand across heterogeneous households. The challenge is twofold. First, the design of volumetric and peak-based grid tariffs sends different incentives that can redistribute costs in ways that are not straightforward to anticipate at the household level. Second, the effect of any grid tariff depends on each household's technology configuration and level of demand.

Without a structured comparison that varies the grid tariff while keeping household characteristics constant, it is difficult to reason about efficiency, affordability, and distributional impacts.

1.4 Research gap

Many studies consider one grid tariff regime, a narrow user group, or one technology at a time. Few collectively combine multiple grid tariff structures, segmentation by household technology portfolios and demand categories, and side-by-side scenarios of higher technology adoption. Investigations that bring these elements together for Austria are underway, but a consolidated household-level comparison remains to be established. This thesis responds by evaluating grid tariff design and household heterogeneity within one consistent framework and by comparing outcomes under alternative adoption scenarios.

1.5 Research question and objectives

This thesis examines how grid tariff design influences household electricity costs and peak demand in Austria. The research question is: *How do volumetric and peak-based grid tariffs affect household electricity costs and peak demand in households with different portfolios of distributed generation and flexible household technologies in Austria?* The study (i) classifies households by flexibility and annual demand, (ii) compares outcomes under two adoption scenarios (baseline and stress-test), and (iii) evaluates how alternative grid tariff structures change costs and peak metrics in the full set of technology combinations.

1.6 Method overview

The analysis evaluates 60 households under three grid tariff structures: volumetric, yearly peak, and monthly peak, and two technology adoption scenarios. A time-resolved optimization represents the operation of the household within technical limits and the consumption of scheduling and available technologies at the temporal resolution of the study. Electricity cost is computed from grid imports, grid-tariff components, and applicable fees, net of any revenues from surplus feed-in where relevant. Peak-based charges are calculated from each household's maximum demand as

defined by the annual or monthly peak component of the respective grid tariff. The results are examined in aggregate, by household flexibility category and technology combination, with percentage changes in electricity costs, grid-related charges, and peak load metrics reported to reveal distribution patterns and design sensitivities.

1.7 Scope and assumptions

The study focuses on household-level economics and peak metrics and does not simulate network power flows or feeder-level constraints. Behavioral learning is not modeled; the optimization isolates the effect of grid-tariff incentives within technical limits. Profiles are representative rather than real-time field data; Austrian-relevant grid tariff definitions and cost components are used so that findings speak to national discussions while remaining interpretable in a broader European context.

1.8 Structure of the thesis

The literature review situates grid-tariff design, household flexibility, equity considerations, and Austrian policy developments and identifies the gaps this study addresses; it also states the specific contributions relative to prior work to avoid redundancy here. The methodology sets out the optimization framework, scenarios, grid-tariff definitions, datasets, and evaluation metrics. The results present aggregate and household-level outcomes across grid-tariff structures and adoption scenarios, highlighting differences by flexibility category and technology combination. The discussion interprets these outcomes for households, distribution system operators, and policymakers, connecting the findings to current European practice and the Austrian context. The conclusion synthesizes the main insights, acknowledges key limitations, and outlines focused avenues for future research.

2 State-of-the-art technology

2.1 Legal and institutional framework shaping the electricity grid

The electricity grid is shaped by comprehensive laws, policies, and regulatory institutions that ensure its reliability, efficiency, and long-term sustainability. In Austria and across the European Union, the interaction between distribution system operators (DSOs), transmission system operators (TSOs), and consumers is shaped by a set of directives, market rules, and governance frameworks. These frameworks are particularly important as they influence grid tariffs, market participation, demand-side flexibility, and the integration of distributed generation and flexible household technologies.

This section explores the key regulations and policies that impact the electricity grid, with a specific focus on their implications for DSOs, household consumers, and tariff structures. It outlines the most relevant laws from the European Union and Austria that set the foundation for future grid tariff models and strategies for peak load reduction.

European Union (EU) legislation

The **Directive (EU) 2024/1711**, amending *Directives (EU) 2018/2001* and *(EU) 2019/944*, advances market design by revisiting tariff formation, data transparency, and planning obligations [1]. It strengthens requirements for cost-reflective and transparent grid tariffs so that DSO cost recovery aligns with fair consumer pricing; enhances network transparency by requiring DSOs to publish real-time information on available connection capacity; and promotes demand-response participation, enabling consumers to shift consumption to off-peak periods to reduce costs. The Directive also reinforces coordinated investment planning by requiring DSOs and TSOs to integrate forecasts of future renewable capacity, thereby supporting proactive infrastructure development consistent with long-term transition goals. For this thesis, these provisions provide the legal basis for grid-tariff structures that both recover DSO costs and reward households for shifting demand and integrating *distributed generation and flexible household technologies*, which is central to the analysis of economic effects and peak load reduction [1].

Complementing the Directive, the **Regulation (EU) 2024/1747**, amending *Regulations (EU) 2019/942* and *(EU) 2019/943*, operationalizes transparency and flexibility in market operation. It mandates cost-reflective tariffs designed to incentivize demand-side flexibility and energy storage, thus reducing reliance on physical grid reinforcements, and requires real-time publication of grid capacity availability to inform investors and owners of *distributed generation and flexible household technologies*. The regulation further introduces peak-shaving mechanisms under which system operators may procure flexibility services to manage peak loads efficiently; obliges DSOs and TSOs to publish joint reports on available grid capacity to coordinate expansion; and encourages anticipatory investments in smart grids and storage to prepare for higher shares of variable renewables. In the context of this thesis, these measures create targeted incentives and mechanisms through which households can provide flexibility and receive tariff-based compensation, directly linking the legal framework to the modeled tariff designs and their expected impacts on household costs and peak-load contributions [2].

Austrian legislation

Electricity act (Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz, EIWOG)

The *EIWOG act* is an Austrian federal law that governs the structure and operation of the electricity industry [3] and provides the legal basis for the *Systemnutzungsentgelteverordnung* (SNE-VO). It is the ordinance that specifies the Austrian grid tariffs (network user charges) [27].

Energy Control act – E-Control act

The *E-Control act* is an Austrian federal law that governs the regulation of the electricity and natural gas markets. It establishes the E-Control as the independent regulatory body responsible for ensuring a competitive, transparent, and efficient energy market while complying with the regulations of the European Union (EU) [4].

Electricity Consumption Reduction act (Stromverbrauchsreduktionsgesetz SVRG)

In Austria, the SVRG provides a concrete legal channel for event-based demand-side response during system-critical or high-price periods. Implemented through APG's

electricity-saving product, SVRG operationalizes consumer participation in targeted peak hour reductions with the dual aims of easing price pressure and limiting fossil resource use, in accordance with the European Emergency Measures framework. In the context of this thesis, SVRG functions as the national bridge between legal intent and household action: it allows households, particularly those with *distributed generation and flexible household technologies*, to supply targeted flexibility of short duration. Importantly, SVRG complements cost-reflective grid tariffs rather than replacing them. While grid tariffs shape daily consumption profiles, SVRG concentrates incentives on specific high-risk hours, creating a layered incentive structure that can reinforce peak load mitigation and cost outcomes analyzed in this work [5].

2.2 Current grid tariff model in Austria

The main function of the electricity grid is to deliver electricity. Grid operators are responsible for maintaining these infrastructure systems, ensuring that electricity reaches consumers safely. To fund their operations, grid operators charge a fee, known as the **grid tariff**. This sector operates as a natural monopoly, as it would be economically inefficient to build a grid in parallel to an existing one. Hence, in Austria, the electricity grid system is regulated by **E-Control**, and they ensure that grid fees are set at fair levels.

The electricity grid is organized into seven grid levels based on rated voltages, as shown in table 2.1 [6]. These levels range from the highest transmission voltages that move electricity over long distances to the lowest voltages that supply households. Grid users are charged according to the cost of providing access at the relevant grid level.

Table 2.1: Grid levels and rated voltages in Austria [6]

Grid level	Rated voltage
1	Extra-high voltage (380 kV and 220 kV, including 380/220-kV transformer voltage)
2	Transformation from extra-high voltage to high voltage
3	High voltage (110 kV, including systems with an operating voltage of more than 36 kV and up to 220 kV)
4	Transformation from high to medium voltage
5	Medium voltage (operating voltage between more than 1 kV up to and including 36 kV, including intermediate voltages)
6	Transformation from medium to low voltage
7	Low voltage (1 kV and below)

This thesis focuses exclusively on **Grid level 7** (low voltage, ≤ 1 kV) as the household supply level for analyzing grid tariffs, household costs, and peak-load contributions.

The electricity bills of consumers include two main components: the cost of electricity itself, which is purchased from the energy suppliers, and the grid fee, which covers the cost of transporting electricity through the grid. In this thesis, the analysis focuses on the grid tariffs; the electricity tariff and all other bill components are held constant for all households.

In Austria, household grid tariffs comprise multiple components. At the framework level, the grid use tariff includes both an energy-dependent element (kWh-based) and a capacity concept. However, for typical household connections at Network Level 7 with *not-measured power*, there is *no demand-metered power charge*. Instead, households pay the kWh-based grid use component together with a yearly fixed fee, and a separate kWh-based grid losses tariff also applies.

2.3 Related literature

2.3.1 Tariff design evolution: Volumetric to capacity-based structures

The design of distribution grid tariffs has gradually evolved from simple volumetric charging mechanisms toward capacity-based structures that more accurately reflect the drivers of network costs. Traditional volumetric tariffs, based on energy consumption (€/MWh), have the advantage of simplicity but increasingly fail to align charges with cost causation in systems with high adoption of distributed generation and flexible household technologies. Peak demand, rather than total energy use, drives long-term investment in network reinforcement, which means that volumetric tariffs can misallocate costs and weaken incentives for peak reduction. Comparative analyses show that capacity-based components, which charge for contracted or measured peak power, offer stronger cost reflectivity and can reduce inefficiencies caused by overreliance on energy-based billing [9, 13]. From a consumer perspective, such designs introduce price signals that directly reward peak management, while for DSOs they create a charging structure more proportional to the capacity costs imposed by each user.

In Austria, the prevailing grid tariff structure remains largely volumetric, recovering costs for transmission and distribution losses, metering, network maintenance, expansion, and ancillary services through energy-based charges. However, recent national initiatives signal a shift toward capacity-oriented designs. The INNOnet project represents a key milestone in this transition, involving over 1,000 residential participants in Netz Oberösterreich, Linz Netz, and Energienetze Steiermark. Its large-scale field trials tested three variable household-level grid tariffs under real conditions, moving beyond purely volume-based charging to load-based pricing logic. The trial objectives included assessing consumer acceptance, determining the lead time requirements for tariff information, and supporting the DSOs in forming a common position on feasible future tariff structures for the Austrian grid sector [7]. This work was informed by forward-looking parameters for 2030–2040, which explains the increased adoption of e-mobility, heat pumps, and photovoltaics.

Evidence from both simulation and empirical studies supports the operational and economic advantages of capacity-based designs. For DSOs, these tariffs facilitate more efficient network operation and long-term planning by providing predictable capacity-linked revenues while maintaining overall income through revenue neutrality mechanisms. Optimization-based studies have shown how restructuring

charges towards capacity metrics can redistribute costs in proportion to actual network utilization without undermining financial stability [9, 10]. From the consumer side, capacity-based designs alter the optimization logic in household energy management systems: for example, graduated tariffs that escalate once quarter-hourly consumption exceeds set thresholds incentivize households to smooth demand peaks, which in turn supports grid stability.

Methodological approaches to evaluate capacity-based tariffs have become increasingly sophisticated. Early conceptual analyses have been expanded through multi-criterion decision analysis frameworks that incorporate stakeholder priorities into quantitative performance indicators [11]. Advanced optimization models now integrate cost driver analysis with probabilistic scenario matrices to account for uncertainty in future demand and technology adoption [12]. Large-scale demonstrations such as INNOnet bridge the gap between modeling and practice, testing both manual and automated control systems to evaluate how real households respond to peak-oriented price signals [7]. Collectively, these developments illustrate a clear trajectory: as distribution networks face higher electrification and flexibility levels, tariff design is moving toward capacity-based structures that can better align consumer incentives with the technical and economic needs of the grid.

2.3.2 Household technology flexibility and demand response (DR) effectiveness

The flexibility potential of households is closely tied to the adoption of distributed generation and flexible household technologies such as photovoltaics (PV), battery storage, electric vehicles (EVs), and heat pumps (HPs). The interplay between these technologies and grid tariff design determines both the economic outcomes for consumers and the peak load implications for the distribution system.

Early research showed why DR from households depends less on tariff labels and more on how signals interact with available flexibility. Under volumetric or fixed charges, growing EV charging quickly breaks the link between charges and cost causation: peaks surge, transformer reinforcement is triggered, and the tariff no longer reflects who drives those costs; by contrast, capacity- or power-based elements incentivize lower charging power and cap feeder peaks [13]. At the consumer side, batteries, EVs, and HPs re-optimize when faced with explicit power/peak signals: batteries can time-shift energy to flatten the household profile, EV charging can be slowed or deferred, and HPs offer thermal shifting windows. These operational levers

explain why later studies consistently find that, as flexible technologies penetrate, volumetric tariffs perform poorly in efficiency and peak management [11, 13].

When high shares of flexible households enter the system, the tariff performance diverges. In a Swiss evaluation framework, a low-flexibility scenario consists of 92% inflexible users and only 2–4% EV or PV users, whereas a high-flexibility scenario is dominated by extended self-consumers (EV+PV+battery) at 50% [11]. Under such high-flex conditions, volumetric tariffs perform worst in efficiency and cost-reflection indicators, whereas power-based designs rank higher, with PV+battery particularly responsive to monthly and yearly peak charges. Batteries actively reduce peaks by shifting either PV feed-in or grid purchases, especially for inflexible households that gain the most from smoothing. From a DSO perspective, this results in lower aggregated peaks and contracted capacities. These are the very proxies used to reflect usage and capacity related costs. Hence, stronger performance of peak-sensitive tariffs as flexible penetration rises. For consumers, these same peak signals matter because tariff prices are set on power metrics (e.g., 7.5 CHF/kW monthly, 90 CHF/kW yearly/capacity), directly rewarding household peak management [11].

Synergies are clearest when PV, batteries, and EV charging are co-optimized: PV provides midday surplus; the battery time-shifts it or arbitrages grid energy; and managed EV charging avoids the evening spike. This is the configuration that dominates high-flexibility scenarios and yields the strongest cost-reduction ordering for PV+battery under peak-based tariffs [11]. A practical confirmation from large-scale field experience is the UK’s Demand Flexibility Service, where roughly one million households averaged an 18% peak event reduction [14]. Demonstrating that even modest in-home capabilities can deliver material peak relief at scale, which is highly salient for DSOs planning reinforcement deferral. Looking across studies, a consistent technology hierarchy for household DR emerges: (i) batteries provide the most immediate, controllable short-term peak shaving; (ii) managed EV charging is the next-best lever for reducing evening peaks; (iii) HPs add thermal storage windows that can be leveraged by peak-based signals; and (iv) PV alone mainly boosts self-consumption but is less effective on evening network peaks without storage. For DSOs, this hierarchy is directly linked to avoided capacity upgrades. For consumers, it aligns with cost savings when tariffs price the peak capacity explicitly. The work linking tariff design to avoided network risk demonstrates how DSOs can quantify and pass through the flexibility value: indicative tariff reductions of 0-42% for existing flexible loads (and 1-22% for future ones) and a 24% network cost reduction under a risk-neutral price control framework. [12].

2.3.3 Economic distribution effects and household heterogeneity

Early comparative work already indicated that who gains (or pays) under peak-oriented tariffs depends on household portfolios and usage intensity, rather than a uniform average customer. According to extensive Danish data, Individual Peak Pricing (IPP) significantly increases costs for users with high levels of technology. EV owners see annual volumetric grid cost increases up to 72.75% (approximately €180/year), while heat pump (HP) owners face +7.56% to +31.13% depending on the IPP threshold [9]. Small apartments generally pay less, and large houses without technologies pay even more [9]. DSOs see trends like cost-driver alignment, increased electrified loads driving demands for reinforcement, and customers facing cost risk with flexible technologies unless they receive operational responsiveness. The same study shows that a congestion-triggered design, Dynamic Critical Peak Pricing (DCPP), reallocates costs less aggressively than IPP and can even reduce EV owners' grid expenses while shifting more to HP users. This illustrates that not only the portfolio but also tariff mechanics shape distributional outcomes [9].

As tariff designs incorporate dynamic triggers, differences by income and occupancy become important. Under a hybrid Dynamic Critical Individual Peak Pricing (DCIPP) scheme, single low-income households without an EV or heat pump save about 3.6% annually, while single high-income households save 1.66–2.28%. Savings decrease as occupancy increases, and households of three to four people face surcharges across income groups. Large households pay approximately 4-6.44% more, with low-income households slightly worse off, partly due to the higher average occupancy [9]. Concurrently, a European indicator study demonstrates that, in contrast to linear energy-based tariffs, capacity/peak-based designs have strong cost reflectivity and refrain from charging high-flex users a lower price. These slope differences widen as the flexibility increases [11]. For DSOs, this supports equity screens alongside efficiency, and for consumers, it clarifies why distributed generation and flexible household technologies can both unlock DR value and concentrate charges if signals cannot be followed.

The measured behavior corroborates the modeled heterogeneity. In Great Britain's Demand Flexibility Service, around one million households registered, and active participants cut demand by an average of 18% during notified events [14]. On the local market scale, the EU Local Energy Markets (LEM) modeling shows a pronounced redistribution between flexible and inflexible participants: the former reduce bills by **21.3%** on average, while the latter's bills rise by 109.5% [10]. For consumers, this underscores why multitechnology readiness and automation (e.g. managed EV

charging or HP preheating) are prerequisites for capturing benefits, and for DSOs, it motivates guardrails (crediting, rebates, and minimum-service guarantees) so tariff reforms remain socially acceptable while preserving cost-reflectivity.

2.3.4 DSO economic impacts and regulatory framework

From a Distribution System Operator (DSO) perspective, shifting from volumetric to peak and capacity sensitive tariffs is fundamentally about aligning revenue recovery with the drivers of network cost while preserving predictable incentives for household flexibility. In Austria, INNOnet pilots operationalize this logic by classifying hours into non-critical, alert, and critical states on a day-ahead basis and communicating the corresponding network tariff levels to customers. This grid-serving design links the tariff strength with expected low-voltage stress and brings cost causation closer to the point of use [7].

Other European studies further show that how DSOs collect revenue matters for fairness and efficiency as flexible technologies scale. Under high flexibility, tariffs that price contracted capacity and peaks retain a strong correlation between charges and cost-driving factors, whereas purely volumetric tariffs begin to under-charge households that contribute disproportionately to network peaks. The slope of the relationship between the charges paid and the cost contribution also drifts away from one in volumetric designs as electrification increases, signaling a loss of cost-reflectiveness [11]. The feeder-level simulations illuminate a mechanism: when EV penetration grows, volumetric tariffs fail to price the peak contributions that drive transformer upgrades, while partly power-based or capacity-subscription designs limit charging power and curb peaks, containing reinforcement needs [13].

Tariff reform interacts with regulation through price control mechanics, revenue allowances, and explicit recognition of the investment value of flexibility. A risk-neutral price control framework shares uncertainty of load growth between DSOs and users and makes the value of flexibility visible via tariff credits [12]. Within an incentive-based regime, allowed returns and performance incentives link earnings to totex efficiency (savings vs. the allowed total expenditure) and service quality [12, 17]. In a system demonstration, this approach reduces total estimated network costs on the order of 24% under severe uncertainty and issues indicative tariff declines (for example, 0-42% for existing flexible loads and 1-22% for future ones), aligning household signals with avoided investment while maintaining revenue adequacy [12].

European best-practice discussions situate these choices within broader market design and equity considerations. Recent analysis notes that while more granular

locational signals could, in principle, improve siting and utilization of flexibility, distributional impacts and implementation complexity are non-trivial; the current European reform path therefore emphasizes alternative means of improving network price signals without moving to full locational marginal pricing (LMP) at the distribution level. This is enhanced by governance lessons gained from fieldwork with the Demand Flexibility Service in Great Britain: About one million households registered, and active participants delivered average event-period demand reductions around 18%, illustrating that clear remuneration and communication can mobilize residential DR at scale; at the same time, policies from the crisis era should remain targeted and temporary to avoid unintended distributional harms [14].

Implications for Austria. For DSOs in Austria, three elements form a coherent package: (i) peak-sensitive tariff elements tested in INNOnet (day-ahead, grid-state-linked levels), (ii) fairness and effectiveness indicators that remain robust as flexibility penetrates (correlation and slope metrics) [11], and (iii) risk-neutral price control with explicit flexibility credits that preserve revenue stability while rewarding measurable peak reduction [12, 17]. Together, these instruments encourage the deployment and operational use of distributed generation and flexible household technologies where they deliver the greatest network value, without sacrificing cost recovery or social acceptability [13, 14].

2.3.5 Research gaps and contribution

This thesis addresses several interconnected research gaps in the study of flexible grid tariff designs within the Austrian low-voltage context. First, it explicitly distinguishes household categories based on their technology portfolios: very flexible, flexible, and inflexible. This segmentation enables a more precise analysis of how multitechnology households (e.g., PV, BESS, HP, and EV combinations) respond differently to peak-based versus volumetric grid tariffs. Second, it provides quantitative evidence on individual household bill outcomes under alternative grid tariff structures, using a data set tailored to the Upper Austrian region. Third, the study integrates these household profiles into a modeling framework, assigning technologies according to defined categories, and applying three grid tariff designs, two of which (yearly peak and monthly peak) were developed specifically for this work. Fourth, the modeling uses the IESopt optimization tool, which has not yet been applied in this context.

By linking these technical findings to a policy roadmap, the thesis bridges the gap between modeled results and actionable tariff reform pathways for Austria.

This synthesis aims to inform regulators and DSOs on how household flexibility, when properly incentivized, can contribute to both cost-reflective grid operation and broader energy transition objectives.

3 Methodology

3.1 Description of households

The analysis framework developed in this thesis is based on a sample of 60 households. Each data set includes annual electricity load profiles in quarter-hour resolution and descriptive information on household characteristics, provided by the partnering organization, **AIT Austrian Institute of Technology**. The load profiles were originally generated using the LoadProfileGenerator [18].

The households are classified into three categories according to their level of flexibility potential. Following this, the profiles are subsequently modified by integrating distributed generation and flexible household technologies according to the scenario-specific adoption rates. This section discusses these aspects, the classification of household flexibility, and the integration of technology in detail.

Household flexibility classification

The households are classified into flexibility categories based on their likelihood of adopting distributed generation and flexible household technologies. These categories indicate the varying likelihoods of integrating photovoltaic (PV) systems, battery energy storage systems (BESS), heat pumps (HPs), and electric vehicles (EVs), reflecting the underlying socio-economic conditions.

Very flexible households have the highest likelihood of adopting flexible technologies, typically associated with higher income levels and stable full-time employment. They exhibit the greatest probability of adopting multiple technologies and thus offer significant potential for load shifting and grid interaction.

Flexible households have a moderate likelihood of adopting one or more flexible technologies. They generally represent medium income levels with stable or part-time employment, enabling partial investments in energy flexibility assets.

Inflexible households are classified by a limited or no likelihood of adopting distributed generation or storage technologies due to socioeconomic constraints such as lower income, unemployment, retirement, or student status. Consequently, their ability to adjust or shift energy consumption in response to tariff structures is minimal.

This classification provides a clear framework for analyzing how households with different levels of flexibility respond to varying grid tariff designs. It also supports a deeper evaluation of the economic impacts on households and the operational implications for distribution system operators (DSOs), including the potential to reduce the need for grid reinforcement.

Distributed generation and flexible household technologies

Photovoltaic (PV) system

PV generation profiles for three panel orientations: east, south, and west are generated using the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) for the location of Linz. Each household is randomly assigned one of these orientations [19]. The size of each photovoltaic system is determined on the basis of the annual electricity consumption of the household. Households consuming less than 3 MWh per year are assigned a 4 kWp system. Those with consumption between 3 and 5 MWh assigned a 6 kWp system, while households consuming between 5 and 8 MWh are assigned a 8 kWp system. For consumption above 8 MWh, a 10 kWp system is used. This sizing approach is a modeling assumption; roof area or financial constraints are not considered.

Battery energy storage systems (BESS)

In this study an assumed battery capacity range of 10–20 kWh is considered for residential households. This assumption is supported by observed trends toward storage capacities and by segmentation of the BESS in the common market, which typically falls below 20 kWh in size [20]. The battery capacity is assigned according to the annual electricity consumption of each household. Households with consumption below 5 MWh are equipped with a 10 kWh battery, rated at 4.4 kW for both charging and discharging. For households consuming between 5 and 10 MWh, a 15 kWh battery, rated at 6.7 kW, is used. Households with consumption above 10 MWh are equipped with a 20 kWh battery, rated 8.9 kW. For modeling purposes, the rated charging and discharging powers are assumed to be equal and correspond to the nominal power values. These parameter choices align with the specifications of commercially available residential battery systems [21].

Heat pumps (HPs)

AIT provides coefficient of performance (COP) profiles along with timeseries data for space heating demand and domestic hot water (DHW) demand [18, 22]. For modeling purposes, the space heating demand is approximated as four times the DHW demand, following typical Austrian household energy end-use distributions, where space heating accounts for approximately 75–80% and DHW accounts for 15–20% of residential energy consumption [23]. This assumption is mathematically expressed as

$$l_{i,t}^{\text{sh}} = \text{Heat demand profile} \cdot 4 \cdot l_{i,t}^{\text{wh}} \quad (3.1)$$

A household is modeled to have two separate air source heat pumps (ASHPs): one for space heating and one for DHW. ASHPs are the predominant technology in Austrian households, with underfloor heating systems commonly used in newer installations, while radiator-based systems remain prevalent in older buildings. Based on these distinctions, a Very Flexible and Flexible household is modeled with ASHPs supplying underfloor heating, while an Inflexible household is modeled with radiator-based ASHPs. [24].

The maximum capacity of each heat pump is determined based on the respective heat demand profiles and the COP values provided. Both the space heating and DHW heat pumps are modeled with integrated thermal storage tanks to reflect operational flexibility. The storage energy capacity for each tank is calculated as the product of peak heating demand and the assigned storage duration.

For space heating, the storage capacity is given by:

$$e_{i,t}^{\text{sh}} = p_{\text{space}}^{\text{peak}} \cdot t_{\text{space}} \quad (3.2)$$

where $e_{i,t}^{\text{sh}}$ represents the space heating thermal storage capacity in MWh, $p_{\text{space}}^{\text{peak}}$ is the peak space heating demand in MW, and t_{space} is the storage duration in hours. For a Very Flexible and Flexible household, the storage duration t_{space} is assigned based on peak demand: households with demand below 1 kW are assigned 1 hour, those between 1 and 2 kW receive 1.5 hours, 2 to 3 kW receive 2 hours, 3 to 4 kW receive 2.5 hours, 4 to 5 kW receive 3 hours, and those above 5 kW are assigned 5 hours. In contrast, an Inflexible household is assigned a storage duration of 0.5 hours, regardless of their peak space heating demand, to reflect their limited operational flexibility.

Similarly, the DHW storage capacity is calculated as:

$$e_{i,t}^{\text{wh}} = p_{\text{water}}^{\text{peak}} \cdot t_{\text{water}} \quad (3.3)$$

where $e_{i,t}^{\text{wh}}$ denotes the DHW thermal storage capacity in MWh, $p_{\text{water}}^{\text{peak}}$ is the peak DHW demand in MW, and t_{water} is the assigned storage duration in hours. For a Very Flexible and Flexible household, the storage duration is determined by the peak DHW demand: 3–5 kW corresponds to 1 hour, 5–7 kW to 2 hours, 7–9 kW to 3 hours, 9–11 kW to 3.5 hours, and values above 11 kW are assigned 5 hours. An Inflexible household is assigned a fixed storage duration of 0.5 hours, again reflecting their limited capacity for demand flexibility.

In this study, households that are not equipped with heat pumps are assumed to use district heating or gas boilers for their thermal needs. As these systems do not rely on electricity for operation, they are considered electrically inflexible in the heating domain and are therefore excluded from the analysis of this thesis.

Electric vehicles (EVs)

EV load profiles are generated based on a hypothetical charging behavior model developed specifically for this study. Different charging rules are applied for weekdays, Saturdays, Sundays, and public holidays to reflect plausible residential charging behavior. Although the structure of the model is theoretical, official Austrian public holidays are incorporated to more realistically represent periods of extended home presence [25].

A key assumption in the model is that all EV charging occurs exclusively at home, without access to public or workplace charging infrastructure. This constraint is essential to assess the impact of home EV charging on residential load profiles and peak demand under different grid tariff designs.

The model assumes that EVs charge only at home using an 11 kW AC charger. The charging windows vary by day type. On weekdays, overnight charging is allowed between 23:00 and 04:00. On Saturdays, charging begins at a randomly selected hour between 00:00 and 04:00 and continues for four hours. On Sundays and public holidays, EVs charge continuously for four hours starting from a random time between 10:00 and 16:00.

When the EV is not charging, the energy demand reflects either standby losses or driving consumption. Standby losses are modeled using a uniform random distribution between 0.1 and 0.5 kW, while driving demand ranges from 1 to 5.5 kW,

depending on the time and type of day. The model outputs a binary connection status labeled 'connected', where a value of 0.011 MW indicates that the EV is actively connected to the grid for charging and a value of 0 indicates disconnection. Public holidays are treated in the same way as Sundays, with flexible charging behavior.

Each generator run produces a unique load profile due to the use of randomized parameters, including connection probability, charging start times, and energy demand levels. Consequently, multiple different EV load profiles are created and assigned to different households within the model.

EV ownership is assigned to households according to their flexibility category and baseline annual electricity consumption. The households classified as Very Flexible and Flexible are assumed to own an EV. This allocation method is used solely for modeling purposes and does not attempt to replicate real-world ownership patterns.

For households equipped with EVs, battery capacity is assigned based on the household's annual electricity consumption. Households consuming between 2 and 3 MWh are assigned an EV with a 58 kWh battery. Those consuming between 3 and 5 MWh are assigned a 64 kWh battery, while households with annual consumption exceeding 5 MWh receive a 72 kWh battery.

The integration of distributed generation and flexible household technologies significantly shapes household electricity consumption profiles and peak demand patterns. These are critical for evaluating the impacts of different grid tariff structures. As a result, the model captures different levels of household flexibility and supports the evaluation of impacts on distribution system operators (DSOs).

3.2 Grid tariffs

For investigation, three grid tariff designs are implemented, each of which represents a distinct pricing approach used to control or encourage household electricity use.

3.2.1 Volumetric grid tariff

A volumetric grid tariff charges households based on the total amount of electricity demand from the grid, with a fixed rate applied in euros per megawatt hour (€/MWh). This grid tariff serves as the baseline in this study and is used for comparison with the other two grid tariff designs.

The volumetric grid tariff for each household is calculated as follows:

$$\sum_t l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot c_i^{\text{vol}}$$

where $l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}}$ is the grid electricity demand [MWh], c_i^{vol} is the volumetric grid tariff for household i [€/MWh].

3.2.2 Yearly peak grid tariff

A yearly peak grid tariff charges each household based on its highest observed 15-minute average power demand from the grid over the course of the year. The charge is applied as a fixed €/MW rate to this single peak value, regardless of when it occurs.

The grid tariff rate is calculated by dividing the total grid cost across all households under the volumetric grid tariff by the sum of their yearly peak capacities:

$$c_i^{\text{peak}} = \frac{\sum_i \sum_t l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot c_i^{\text{vol}}}{\sum_i p_i^{\text{vol}}}$$

It is important to note that the sum of the peak capacities $\sum_i p_i^{\text{vol}}$ is derived from the consumption profiles generated under the baseline volumetric grid tariff scenario. The peak tariff rate c_i^{peak} is calibrated to ensure that the total grid revenue remains equal to that of the baseline.

The yearly peak grid cost for each household is then calculated as:

$$p_i^{\text{peak}} \cdot c_i^{\text{peak}}$$

where p_i^{peak} is the yearly peak capacity of household i [MW], and c_i^{peak} is the corresponding tariff rate [€/MW].

3.2.3 Monthly peak grid tariff

A monthly peak grid tariff charges each household based on its highest observed 15-minute average power demand from the grid in each calendar month. The charge is applied as a fixed €/MW rate to the peak value in each month, resulting in twelve individual peak charges over the year.

The grid tariff rate is calculated by dividing the total grid cost across all households under the volumetric grid tariff by the sum of all monthly peak capacities across all

households:

$$c_i^{\text{mpeak}} = \frac{\sum_i \sum_t l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot c_i^{\text{vol}}}{\sum_i \sum_{m=1}^{12} p_{i,m}^{\text{vol}}}$$

As with the yearly peak tariff, the monthly peak capacities $p_{i,m}^{\text{vol}}$ are derived from the grid consumption profiles produced under the baseline volumetric tariff scenario. The resulting tariff rate c_i^{mpeak} is calibrated to maintain revenue neutrality with the baseline.

The monthly peak grid cost for each household is calculated as:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{12} p_{i,m}^{\text{peak}} \cdot c_i^{\text{mpeak}}$$

where $p_{i,m}^{\text{peak}}$ is the monthly peak capacity of the household i in month m [MW], and c_i^{mpeak} is the corresponding tariff rate [€/MW].

3.3 Total costs

The total annual cost for each household comprises electricity charges determined by the optimization model and, where applicable, a fixed gas heating charge added in post-processing. The electricity cost is calculated by taking into account the electricity demand from the grid, applicable tariffs, and revenues from electricity feed-in (surplus) to the grid. The following formulation is used:

$$C_i^{\text{elec}} = \sum_t \left[l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot \left(c_i^{\text{ene}} + c_i^{\text{grid}} + c_i^{\text{fees}} \right) - s_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot c_i^{\text{fi}} \right]$$

where $l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}}$ is the electricity demand from the grid [MWh], $s_{i,t}^{\text{grid}}$ is the surplus electricity to the grid [MWh], c_i^{ene} is the energy price [€/MWh], c_i^{grid} is the grid tariff, which varies by design [€/MWh or €/MW], c_i^{fees} is the combined value of taxes and levies [€/MWh], c_i^{fi} is the feed-in tariff for surplus electricity to the grid [€/MWh].

For households without a heat pump, an additional term accounts for space and water heating energy delivered by a conventional gas boiler or district heating interface. Because this demand does not affect the electrical dispatch, it is treated as an exogenous cost:

$$C_i^{\text{gas}} = \begin{cases} Q_i^{\text{heat}} \cdot c^{\text{gas}}, & \text{if no heat pump is installed} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where Q_i^{heat} is the annual thermal load (in MWh), and $c^{\text{gas}} = 128.01$ €/MWh is the average retail gas price in Austria for 2025. The total annual cost reported for each household is then calculated as:

$$C_i^{\text{total}} = C_i^{\text{elec}} + C_i^{\text{gas}}$$

Table 3.1: Prices used in total cost calculation (including 20% VAT)

Parameter	Value [€/MWh]
Energy price (c_i^{ene})	185
Grid tariff (baseline, c_i^{vol})	81
Taxes and levies (c_i^{fees})	18
Feed-in tariff (c_i^{fi})	26
Gas price (c^{gas})	128.01

Among the cost components in Table 3.1, only the grid tariff c_i^{grid} is varied in the tariff scenarios. All other parameters remain fixed for all households throughout the analysis. For the baseline scenario, the volumetric grid tariff value is taken from Austrian public sources to reflect current residential pricing. The ‘‘Pauschale’’ (flat-rate network fee) component was excluded from this study to maintain consistency across tariff comparisons.

All prices are based on values from April 2025 [26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

3.4 Optimization tool

IESopt: an Integrated Energy System Optimization framework

In this thesis, household energy optimization is formulated as a linear programming problem and solved using IESopt. It is developed and maintained by the Center for Energy at AIT. IESopt is designed to support the modeling of complex energy systems with a high integration of distributed resources and energy carriers. In the thesis, IESopt is employed specifically to simulate the behavior of residential electricity consumption under different grid tariff designs.

Detailed technical documentation for IESopt is available on GitHub, which describes the tool's full capabilities, code structure, and usage examples [31].

Working of IESopt

Figure 3.1 summarizes the sequential steps involved in the optimization process, from input definition to post-processing of results.

Figure 3.1: Optimization workflow using IESopt [29]

IESopt takes user-defined inputs such as time-series data, system components, technical parameters, constraints, and an objective function. These inputs are provided through configuration files or scripting interfaces.

After the inputs are define, IESopt creates an optimization problem using Julia for Mathematical Programming (JuMP), which formulates it as a linear programming (LP) model. JuMP then forwards this model to the HiGHS solver, which solves the optimization problem using suitable algorithms. After solving, the optimal results are returned to IESopt, where they are further processed to produce energy balance information, cost summaries, and optimized load profiles.

The linear programming in this section is formulated using IESopt. It internally uses JuMP to convert the problem into standard LP form. The final LP formulation is passed to the HiGHS solver.

3.5 Optimization model

Linear programming (LP)

Linear programming (LP) is a widely used mathematical optimization technique for determining the best outcome, such as minimum cost or maximum efficiency, in a model whose requirements are represented by linear relationships. It is particularly well suited for modeling energy systems, where decisions regarding energy flows, storage, and consumption can often be expressed using linear equations and inequalities. An LP problem is defined by three primary components: a linear objective function to be minimized or maximized and a set of constraints that restrict the feasible region. And a set of decision variables that represent the quantities to be optimized. All relationships between variables and parameters must be linear, ensuring computational efficiency and interpretability of results [32].

In the context of this thesis, linear programming is used to model the energy behavior of residential households under different designs of grid tariffs. The LP formulation determines optimal energy consumption patterns that minimize household energy costs while satisfying technical and operational constraints related to distributed generation and flexible household technologies, grid connection, and tariff designs.

The standard form of a linear programming problem is written as:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} \quad \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{x} \tag{3.4}$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}, \tag{3.5}$$

$$\mathbf{x} \geq \mathbf{0}. \tag{3.6}$$

Here, \mathbf{x} denotes the vector of decision variables; \mathbf{c}^T is the transposed coefficient vector for the objective function; \mathbf{A} is the matrix of coefficients for inequality constraints; and \mathbf{b} is the vector of constraint bounds [32].

This representation forms the mathematical foundation for the optimization model applied in this thesis. The subsequent sections present the detailed structure of the

LP formulation, including the objective function, constraints, and decision variables used in the household energy simulations.

Model Parameters and Notation

All variables are defined at the household and quarter-hourly time-step level in Table 3.2 and Table 3.3. That is, each symbol is indexed by household i and time step t (e.g., $l_{i,t}$, $e_{i,t}$) unless explicitly omitted.

Table 3.2: Economic and tariff-related model parameters.

Symbol	Description
C_i^{elec}	Total annual electricity cost for household [€]
$l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}}$	Grid electricity demand [MWh]
$s_{i,t}^{\text{grid}}$	Grid electricity surplus (export) [MWh]
c_i^{ene}	Energy price [€/MWh]
c_i^{fees}	Taxes and levies [€/MWh]
c_i^{fi}	Feed-in tariff for surplus electricity [€/MWh]
c_i^{vol}	Volumetric grid tariff [€/MWh]
p_i^{peak}	Yearly peak capacity [MW]
$p_{i,m}^{\text{peak}}$	Monthly peak capacity [MW]
c_i^{peak}	Yearly peak grid tariff [€/MW]
c_i^{mpeak}	Monthly peak grid tariff [€/MW]

Table 3.3: Technical system parameters.

Symbol	Description
$l_{i,t}$	Annual baseline household electricity demand, excluding flexible technologies [MWh]
$g_{i,t}^{\text{pv}}$	PV electricity generation [MWh]
$d_{i,t}^{\text{bat}}$	Battery discharge [MW]
$u_{i,t}^{\text{bat}}$	Battery charge [MW]
$e_{i,t}^{\text{bat}}$	Battery energy content [MWh]
E_i^{bat}	Maximum battery energy capacity [MWh]
R_i^{bat}	Battery rated charging power [MW]
D_i^{bat}	Battery rated discharging power [MW]
η_u, η_d	Battery charging and discharging efficiencies
$x_{i,t}^{\text{shp}}$	Electric input to space heating heat pump [MWh]
$x_{i,t}^{\text{whp}}$	Electric input to water heating heat pump [MWh]
$e_{i,t}^{\text{sh}}$	Space heating thermal storage level [MWh]
$e_{i,t}^{\text{wh}}$	Hot water thermal storage level [MWh]
$q_{i,t}^{\text{sh}}$	Heat delivered for space heating [MWh]
$q_{i,t}^{\text{wh}}$	Heat delivered for water heating [MWh]
$\text{COP}_{i,t}^{\text{sh}}, \text{COP}_{i,t}^{\text{wh}}$	Coefficients of performance for space and water heating heat pumps
$l_{i,t}^{\text{sh}}, l_{i,t}^{\text{wh}}$	Heat demand for space heating and domestic hot water [MWh]
$E_i^{\text{sh}}, E_i^{\text{wh}}$	Maximum thermal storage capacities [MWh]
$u_{i,t}^{\text{ev}}$	EV charging power [MW]
$l_{i,t}^{\text{ev}}$	EV demand [MW]
$e_{i,t}^{\text{ev}}$	EV battery energy content [MWh]
$A_{i,t}^{\text{ev}}$	Available EV charging power based on connection status [MW]
E_i^{ev}	Maximum EV battery energy capacity [MWh]

Objective function

The objective of the household is to minimize the total annual electricity cost, composed of the electricity demand from the grid, the applicable tariffs, and revenues from electricity feed-in (surplus) to the grid. The corresponding minimization problem is formulated as:

$$\min C_i^{\text{elec}} = \sum_t \left[l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot (c_i^{\text{ene}} + c_i^{\text{vol}} + c_i^{\text{fees}}) - s_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot c_i^{\text{fi}} \right] \quad (3.7)$$

The minimization objective therefore includes energy procurement costs, fixed system fees, export revenues, and the yearly peak grid tariff. The corresponding cost-minimization problem is formulated as:

$$\min C_i^{\text{elec}} = \sum_t \left[l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot (c_i^{\text{ene}} + c_i^{\text{fees}}) - s_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot c_i^{\text{fi}} \right] + p_i^{\text{peak}} \cdot c_i^{\text{peak}} \quad (3.8)$$

The minimization objective reflects both energy usage and monthly peak grid tariff as:

$$\min C_i^{\text{elec}} = \sum_t \left[l_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot (c_i^{\text{ene}} + c_i^{\text{fees}}) - s_{i,t}^{\text{grid}} \cdot 0.25 \cdot c_i^{\text{fi}} \right] + \sum_m \left[p_{i,m}^{\text{peak}} \cdot c_i^{\text{mpeak}} \right] \quad (3.9)$$

Constraints

At each time step, the household must balance its electricity inflows and outflows. Electricity generated by the PV system, drawn from the battery, or imported from the grid must match the combined electricity demand of the household, the battery charging, the EV charging, and the operation of heat pumps:

$$g_{i,t} + g_{i,t}^{\text{PV}} + d_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} = l_{i,t} + s_{i,t} + u_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} + x_{i,t}^{\text{shp}} + x_{i,t}^{\text{whp}} + u_{i,t}^{\text{ev}} \quad (3.10)$$

The following constraints govern the operation of the household battery system, ensuring that energy content evolves consistently with charging and discharging actions, stays within defined limits, and respects rated charging and discharging powers.

Battery energy content dynamics:

$$e_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} = e_{i,t-1}^{\text{bat}} + \eta_u \cdot u_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} - \frac{1}{\eta_d} \cdot d_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} \quad (3.11)$$

Battery energy content bounds:

$$0 \leq e_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} \leq E_i^{\text{bat}} \quad (3.12)$$

Battery charging and discharging power limits:

$$0 \leq u_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} \leq R_i^{\text{bat}} \quad (3.13)$$

$$0 \leq d_{i,t}^{\text{bat}} \leq D_i^{\text{bat}} \quad (3.14)$$

The heat pump and thermal storage operations are governed by constraints that describe the relationships between the input of electricity, the heat delivered, the dynamics of storage energy, and the storage limits. These constraints apply similarly to both space heating ($k = \text{sh}$) and domestic hot water ($k = \text{wh}$) systems.

Heat pump output constraints:

$$q_{i,t}^k = x_{i,t}^{\text{kp}} \cdot \text{COP}_{i,t}^k, \quad k \in \{\text{sh}, \text{wh}\} \quad (3.15)$$

Thermal storage dynamics:

$$e_{i,t}^k = e_{i,t-1}^k + q_{i,t}^k - l_{i,t}^k, \quad k \in \{\text{sh}, \text{wh}\} \quad (3.16)$$

Thermal storage bounds:

$$0 \leq e_{i,t}^k \leq E_i^k, \quad k \in \{\text{sh}, \text{wh}\} \quad (3.17)$$

The electric vehicle (EV) battery operation is governed by energy balance, energy content limits, and charging power availability constraints. Charging and demand profiles in MW are scaled appropriately to update the battery energy content over each timestep.

EV Battery Energy Content Dynamics:

$$e_{i,t}^{\text{ev}} = e_{i,t-1}^{\text{ev}} + \Delta t \cdot u_{i,t}^{\text{ev}} - \Delta t \cdot l_{i,t}^{\text{ev}} \quad (3.18)$$

where $\Delta t = 0.25$ hours.

EV Battery Energy Content Bounds:

$$0 \leq e_{i,t}^{\text{ev}} \leq E_i^{\text{ev}} \quad (3.19)$$

EV Charging Power Limit:

$$0 \leq u_{i,t}^{\text{ev}} \leq A_{i,t}^{\text{ev}} \quad (3.20)$$

Decision variables

The optimization of the decision variables within the model includes the quantities of demand and surplus in the grid ($g_{i,t}, s_{i,t}$), battery charging and discharging power and energy content ($u_{i,t}^{\text{bat}}, d_{i,t}^{\text{bat}}, e_{i,t}^{\text{bat}}$), HP electricity inputs and outputs delivered ($x_{i,t}^{\text{shp}}, x_{i,t}^{\text{whp}}, q_{i,t}^{\text{sh}}, q_{i,t}^{\text{wh}}$), HP thermal storage energy content ($e_{i,t}^{\text{sh}}, e_{i,t}^{\text{wh}}$), EV charging power and energy content ($u_{i,t}^{\text{ev}}, e_{i,t}^{\text{ev}}$), and the peak capacities relevant for tariff calculation ($p_i^{\text{peak}}, p_{i,m}^{\text{peak}}$).

Figure 3.2: Household energy system with integrated cost minimization under grid tariffs.

3.6 Scenario analysis

To assess the impact of varying levels of residential flexibility on grid cost outcomes, two future scenarios are defined: a **Baseline (BAU)** scenario, representing realistic technology penetration aligned with current trends and regional targets, and a **Stress-Test** scenario is a technically plausible upper bound case created by increasing the share of households equipped with distributed generation and flexible household technologies relative to the BAU. It is used to assess how alternative grid-tariff designs influence aggregate outcomes, total costs, electricity expenditures, and peak demand, under higher adoption. Each scenario is simulated across the 60 modeled households (HHs) under all three grid tariff structures to analyze household electricity cost variations and impacts on low-voltage grid peak loads.

Table 3.4: Number of households assigned each technology under the two scenarios

Technology	BAU Scenario (HHs)	Stress-Test Scenario (HHs)
Photovoltaic (PV)	27	36
Battery storage	7	18
Heat pumps (HP)	7	18
Electric vehicles (EV)	7	18

The levels of PV adoption for the BAU scenario in Upper Austria are directly derived from regional renewable energy expansion targets, specifying 3.5 gigawatt-peak (GWp) by 2030 [34]. With assumptions of a 70% rooftop installation share [33], an average residential PV system size of 7.5 kWp [35], and approximately 694,440 households [36], this corresponds to a penetration rate of approximately 45%. For the Stress-Test scenario, a higher penetration rate of 60% is adopted as an upper bound condition, obtained by extrapolating current regional targets and growth trends.

Residential battery energy storage system (BESS) penetration is established through a two-step process. First, the national baseline for 2023 indicates around 94,136 Austrian households equipped with rooftop PV and BESS, representing a battery attachment ratio of approximately 10%, based on approximately 0.85 million PV-equipped households nationwide, a total rooftop PV capacity of 6.3 GW, and an average system size of 7.5 kWp [35, 36, 37]. This baseline is proportionally scaled

to Upper Austria, resulting in approximately 14,120 battery-equipped households (11% regional attachment ratio). Second, future adoption is projected by applying scenario-specific attachment ratios, 25% (BAU) and 50% (Stress-Test), to the previously calculated 2030 regional PV household figures. This resulted in Upper Austrian household penetration levels of approximately 11% and 30%, respectively, for the two scenarios.

The heat pump (HP) and electric vehicle (EV) scenarios are determined by proportionally scaling national-level projections to Upper Austria, which makes up approximately 16.5% of all Austrian households. The national projected 2030 BAU penetrations for HPs and EVs are approximately 456,000 and 505,870 units, respectively [37, 38]. When scaled to Upper Austria, these figures yield approximately 75,240 HPs (11%) and 83,468 EVs (12%). For the Stress-Test scenario, higher penetration rates of 30% for HPs and 30% for EVs are adopted, reflecting upper bound estimates aligned with the Stress-Test design.

The defined scenario penetration values are then proportionally assigned to the 60 modeled households, ensuring consistency and transparency across all inputs of flexible technology as shown in Table 3.4.

A detailed breakdown of the calculations is provided in Appendix 9.

3.7 Limitations of the model

The methodology presented in this study has several limitations. The household profiles and flexible technology configurations are based on available data, which may not capture the full diversity of the real-world households. Although energy prices, taxes, levies, and feed-in tariffs are included for completeness, they are assumed to remain constant throughout the analysis. EV charging is modeled to occur exclusively at home, with no access to public or workplace charging. The optimization relies on linear programming, which, while computationally efficient, does not capture nonlinear system behaviors. User behavior is not modeled, including the override of optimized schedules or the willingness to adopt flexible technologies. Finally, while the default volumetric grid tariff reflects an Austrian case, the other two grid tariff designs are conceptual and used for comparison. In this study, only three tariff types are analyzed, which does not cover the full range of existing or future grid tariff designs.

4 Results and discussion

This chapter presents the results of the simulation-based analysis aimed at evaluating the economic impacts and peak load reduction potential of future grid tariff designs at the low-voltage (LV) grid level. The findings focus on assessing how the application of flexible grid tariffs influences household electricity costs and contributes to reducing peak demand. The results are derived from optimization models applied to 60 households under two scenarios: Baseline (BAU) and Stress-Test, and evaluated across three different grid tariff structures.

The cost levels for yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariffs are calculated based on the results of the volumetric grid tariff simulations for both the BAU and Stress-Test scenarios. The 12 grid costs and peak demand values are initially generated by the optimizer, one for each month. The grid expenses are then totaled, and peak values are averaged to make the computations comparable to the other grid tariffs. These calculated values are then used as input into the model to simulate household electricity costs. Table 4.1 shows the cost values applied for each tariff in both scenarios.

Table 4.1: Calculated grid tariff values

Scenario	Grid tariff type	Grid tariff value (€/MW/yr) or (€/MW/month)
BAU	Yearly peak	49,003
	Monthly peak	4,985
Stress-Test	Yearly peak	51,945
	Monthly peak	5,241

The analysis progresses from the visual identification of consumption patterns (Section 4.1) to the quantitative evaluation of economic and peak demand (Sections 4.2 and 4.3), allowing a comprehensive evaluation of tariff effectiveness in different household and technology configurations.

4.1 Load profile analysis

4.1.1 Heat map for quarter-hourly electricity grid consumption values

This subsection presents quarter-hourly electricity grid consumption patterns across different household flexibility categories and annual demand levels under various grid tariff structures. Heat maps provide a comprehensive visualization of the temporal behavior of consumption throughout the year, revealing daily and seasonal patterns that form the basis for understanding the response of households to different tariff designs of the grid. Each heat map displays consumption data across three tariff structures, with color intensity representing power consumption levels in kilowatts, where darker blue indicates lower consumption, and red represents peak consumption periods.

The heat maps demonstrate a clear progression in consumption intensities across demand categories within each flexibility level. Low annual demand households exhibit consumption patterns predominantly in the lower range of the color scale, with peak consumption rarely exceeding mid-range values. Medium annual demand households show increased consumption intensities with more frequent occurrence of higher-intensity periods, while high annual demand households display the most pronounced consumption patterns with extensive high-intensity coloring. This consumption intensity progression remains consistent across very flexible and flexible household categories.

Distinct seasonal patterns emerge across all demand categories and flexibility levels. Winter months consistently exhibit elevated consumption levels. The transition periods of spring and fall show intermediate consumption levels, whereas the summer months generally display the lowest consumption intensities.

Very flexible households

The very flexible households analyzed incorporate different distributed generation and flexible household technology combinations. Low annual demand households feature photovoltaic systems with heat pumps (PV+HP), medium annual demand households are equipped with photovoltaic systems, battery energy storage systems, and electric vehicles (PV+BESS+EV), while high annual demand households incorporate photovoltaic systems, battery energy storage systems, heat pumps, and electric vehicles (PV+BESS+HP+EV).

Load shifting behavior varies dramatically across demand levels, as illustrated in Figures 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3. The low annual demand household (Figure 4.1) shows minimal responsiveness to changes in tariff structure, with consumption patterns remaining largely unchanged in volumetric, yearly peak, and monthly peak grid tariffs. The scattered red consumption periods, mainly occurring during midday hours (12:00-15:00), persist in the three grid tariff structures with negligible redistribution.

Figure 4.1: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Very flexible low demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

The medium annual demand household (Figure 4.2) exhibits the most pronounced load shifting behavior in response to peak based grid tariffs. Under the volumetric grid tariff structure, intense red consumption is heavily concentrated during the early morning hours (00:00-06:00), creating distinct horizontal bands throughout the year. This concentrated consumption pattern almost completely disappears under both yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariffs, replaced by more distributed blue patterns across different time periods. This dramatic redistribution demonstrates significant load management capabilities when economic incentives encourage reduction in peak demand.

Figure 4.2: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Very flexible medium demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

The high annual demand household (Figure 4.3) displays extensive peak consumption under volumetric grid tariffs, with red periods occurring during both early morning hours (00:00-06:00) and midday periods (12:00-15:00), particularly pronounced during winter months. Under peak based grid tariff structures, these concentrated consumption periods become significantly reduced and more temporally distributed. The winter heating patterns remain evident but show greater dispersion at different hours of the day, indicating effective load shifting while maintaining necessary thermal comfort requirements.

Figure 4.3: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Very flexible high demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

Flexible households

Flexible households show different consumption characteristics and load shifting patterns compared to very flexible households, as illustrated in Figures 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6. The consumption patterns operate on a reduced intensity scale (0.001-0.005 MW) compared to very flexible households. The flexible households analyzed incorporate PV (low demand), PV with BESS (medium demand), and PV with EV (high demand).

The low annual demand household (Figure 4.4) shows minimal variation in consumption patterns across all three tariff grid structures, with consistently low consumption levels throughout the year. The consumption patterns remain virtually unchanged between volumetric, yearly peak, and monthly peak grid tariffs.

Figure 4.4: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Flexible low demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

The medium annual demand household (Figure 4.5) displays some seasonal variation with increased activity during winter months under volumetric grid tariff conditions. Peak based grid tariffs result in subtle redistribution of consumption patterns, though the changes are considerably less pronounced than observed in very flexible households.

Figure 4.5: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Flexible medium demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

The high annual demand household (Figure 4.6) shows pronounced red consumption bands during the early morning hours (00:00-06:00) throughout the year under volumetric grid tariff conditions. These concentrated consumption periods are significantly reduced under both yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariffs, with consumption redistributed across different time periods. The load shifting patterns are notable but remain more constrained compared to very flexible households.

Figure 4.6: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Flexible high demand household under different grid tariff structures:(a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

Inflexible households

Inflexible households exhibit limited consumption pattern variations across tariff structures, as illustrated in Figures 4.7, 4.8, and 4.9. The consumption patterns operate on a similar intensity scale (0.001-0.006 MW) as flexible households. The inflexible households analyzed include no distributed technologies for low and medium annual demand households, while high annual demand households incorporate heat pumps.

The low and medium annual demand inflexible households (Figures 4.7 and 4.8) show minimal consumption variation across all tariff structures with consistently low consumption levels throughout the year.

Figure 4.7: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Inflexible low demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

Figure 4.8: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Inflexible medium demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

Inflexible households with high annual demand (Figure 4.9) show pronounced red consumption during the winter months, particularly during midday and afternoon hours (12:00-18:00), reflecting heating requirements. Under peak based grid tariffs, these winter heating patterns show modest redistribution while maintaining similar overall consumption characteristics.

Figure 4.9: Electricity grid consumption patterns for Inflexible high demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff

4.1.2 Representative profiles by technology combinations

This subsection presents representative electricity grid consumption profiles for different distributed generation and flexible household technology combinations to illustrate varying degrees of responsiveness to grid tariff structures. The analysis examines both annual consumption patterns and seasonal profiles across summer weekdays, summer weekends, winter weekdays, and winter weekends. These representative examples demonstrate how technology configurations influence household ability to modify consumption patterns in response to volumetric, yearly peak, and monthly peak grid tariff designs, providing foundational insights for the subsequent quantitative analysis of peak demand and grid tariff impacts.

Non-technology

Households without distributed generation or flexible technologies exhibit minimal responsiveness to changes in grid tariff structure, as illustrated in Figures 4.10 and

4.11. The annual consumption profile demonstrates consistent power demand levels across all three grid tariff structures, with consumption remaining within a narrow range throughout the year with the exception of brief intervals of sustained low but non-zero demand observed (e.g., late April or mid-summer), consistent with temporary household absence. The consumption pattern shows minimal seasonal variation, as heating and hot water demands are met through district heating systems and do not contribute to the consumption of the electricity grid.

The seasonal profiles reveal typical residential consumption patterns with modest daily variations. Summer weekday and weekend profiles display relatively low consumption levels with minor peaks during evening hours. Winter profiles show similar consumption characteristics with standard residential load patterns during morning and evening periods. Across all seasonal conditions, the consumption patterns remain virtually identical under volumetric, yearly peak, and monthly peak grid tariffs, indicating the absence of load management capabilities. The consistent overlap of the three grid tariff profiles throughout all seasonal conditions demonstrates that households without flexible technologies cannot effectively respond to economic incentives for peak demand reduction.

4 Results and discussion

Figure 4.10: Annual power consumption analysis for household with no technology

Figure 4.11: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with no technology

Only photovoltaic (PV)

Households with PV systems demonstrate limited responsiveness to grid tariff structure changes, as shown in Figures 4.12 and 4.13. The annual consumption profile displays minimal variation across the three grid tariff structures, with consumption patterns remaining largely consistent throughout the year, with the exception of brief intervals of sustained low but non-zero demand observed (e.g., late April or mid-summer), consistent with temporary household absence. The presence of PV generation affects the net grid consumption but does not fundamentally alter the household’s ability to shift consumption timing in response to different grid tariff designs.

The seasonal profiles reveal the influence of PV generation on daily consumption patterns. The summer weekday and weekend profiles show distinctive midday consumption peaks around 09:00-15:00, corresponding to periods when PV output may not fully cover household demand. Winter profiles display different consumption characteristics, with higher overall grid consumption and less pronounced midday variations. However, across all seasonal conditions, the consumption patterns under volumetric, yearly peak, and monthly peak grid tariffs show minimal differentiation. The limited load shifting capability reflects the absence of energy storage or other

flexible technologies that could enable temporal demand redistribution in response to peak-based pricing signals.

Figure 4.12: Annual power consumption analysis for household with only PV

Figure 4.13: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with only PV

Only heat pumps (HPs)

Households with HPs exhibit notable seasonal consumption patterns and demonstrate modest responsiveness to grid tariff structure changes, as illustrated in Figures 4.14 and 4.15. The annual consumption profile shows pronounced seasonal variation with significantly higher consumption during winter months compared to summer periods, reflecting the HPs space heating and hot water requirements. Under different grid tariff structures, the annual profiles display subtle variations, indicating some degree of load management capability through HP operation optimization.

The seasonal profiles reveal distinct consumption characteristics driven by thermal demands. Summer weekday and weekend profiles show relatively low consumption levels with midday peaks around 12:00–15:00, reflecting typical household activities. Winter profiles demonstrate substantially higher consumption levels with multiple daily peaks during morning (06:00–09:00), midday (12:00–15:00), and evening (18:00–21:00) periods, reflecting space heating demands. Across the winter profiles, visible differences emerge between volumetric and peak based grid tariffs, with peak based structures showing some redistribution of high-consumption periods. The thermal mass of the heat pump enables limited load shifting capabilities, allowing consumption timing adjustments while maintaining thermal comfort requirements. However,

4 Results and discussion

the responsiveness remains constrained compared to systems with additional flexibility resources.

Figure 4.14: Annual power consumption analysis for household with only HPs

Figure 4.15: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with only HPs

Photovoltaic (PV) and heat pumps (HPs)

Households with PV systems and HPs demonstrate enhanced responsiveness to tariff structure changes compared to single-technology configurations, as shown in Figures 4.16 and 4.17. The annual consumption profile exhibits pronounced seasonal variation, with higher winter consumption reflecting HP operation for space heating, while the presence of PV generation moderates overall grid consumption levels. Across different grid tariff structures, the annual profiles show some variation, indicating improved load management capabilities through the combination of PV generation and HP flexibility.

The seasonal profiles reveal the combined influence of PV generation and thermal demand management. Summer weekday and weekend profiles display midday consumption patterns influenced by both PV output and typical household activities, with some visible differences between grid tariff structures suggesting modest load shifting capabilities. Winter profiles show substantially higher consumption levels with multiple daily peaks but demonstrate notable differences between volumetric and peak based grid tariffs. The winter weekend profile particularly shows significant load redistribution, with peak based grid tariffs enabling consumption shifting from high-demand periods to more distributed patterns throughout the day. The

combination of PV generation and HP thermal flexibility provides enhanced responsiveness compared to either technology operating independently.

Figure 4.16: Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV and HPs

Figure 4.17: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with photovoltaic and HPs

Photovoltaic (PV) and battery energy storage systems (BESS)

Households with PV systems and BESS demonstrate significant responsiveness to changes in tariff structure, as illustrated in Figures 4.18 and 4.19. The annual consumption profile shows moderate seasonal variation with visible differences between grid tariff structures, indicating the BESS’s ability to enable load management strategies with the exception of a brief interval of sustained low but non-zero demand in late July–early August, consistent with temporary household absence. The presence of energy storage allows for temporal decoupling of consumption and demand, creating opportunities for load shifting in response to peak based pricing signals.

The seasonal profiles reveal substantial load management capabilities enabled by BESS. Summer weekday and weekend profiles show pronounced differences between tariff structures, with peak based grid tariffs enabling redistribution of consumption from high-demand periods around 15:00-18:00 to more distributed patterns throughout the day. Winter profiles demonstrate even more dramatic load shifting capabilities, with volumetric grid tariff profiles showing concentrated consumption peaks around 18:00-21:00 that become significantly redistributed under yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariffs. The winter weekend profile particularly illustrates

4 Results and discussion

the storage system's flexibility, with high consumption periods under the volumetric tariff (reaching above 0.007 MW) becoming substantially flattened and redistributed under peak based structures.

Figure 4.18: Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV and BESS

Figure 4.19: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV and BESS

Photovoltaic (PV) and electric vehicle (EV)

Household with PV system and EV demonstrate substantial response to changes in grid tariff structure, as shown in Figures 4.20 and 4.21. The annual consumption profile exhibits notable variation across different grid tariff structures, indicating significant load management capabilities. The presence of EV charging loads creates opportunities for flexible demand scheduling, particularly when combined with photovoltaic generation to optimize self-consumption patterns.

The seasonal profiles reveal pronounced load shifting behaviors, particularly evident in the EV charging patterns. Summer weekday and weekend profiles show dramatic differences between tariff structures, with volumetric grid tariff profiles displaying concentrated charging events during early morning hours (00:00-03:00) and evening periods (21:00-24:00). Under peak based grid tariffs, these concentrated charging periods become significantly redistributed, with consumption shifting to midday hours when photovoltaic generation may offset some of the charging demand. Winter profiles demonstrate even more substantial load management capabilities, with volumetric grid tariff profiles showing intense early morning charging events (00:00-06:00) reaching above 0.011 MW that become dramatically flattened and redistributed under peak based structures. The winter weekend profile partic-

4 Results and discussion

ularly illustrates the EV's flexibility, with concentrated high-consumption periods shifting to more distributed charging patterns throughout the day.

Figure 4.20: Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV and EV

Figure 4.21: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV and EV

Photovoltaic (PV), battery energy storage systems (BESS) and electric vehicle (EV)

Households with PV systems, BESS, and EV demonstrate exceptional responsiveness to grid tariff structure changes, as illustrated in Figures 4.22 and 4.23. The annual consumption profile shows distinct variations across different grid tariff structures, indicating comprehensive load management capabilities through the integration of multiple flexible technologies. The combination of BESS and controllable EV charging creates extensive opportunities for temporal demand optimization.

The seasonal profiles reveal the most dramatic load shifting behaviors among all technology combinations analyzed. Summer weekday and weekend profiles show substantial differences between grid tariff structures, with volumetric grid tariff profiles displaying concentrated consumption peaks during early morning hours (00:00-06:00) and evening periods (21:00-24:00), reaching above 0.011 MW. Under peak-based grid tariffs, these concentrated periods become dramatically redistributed, with consumption shifting to mid-day hours and creating more balanced daily profiles. Winter profiles demonstrate even more pronounced load management capabilities, with volumetric grid tariff profiles showing intense early morning consumption events (00:00-06:00) that become virtually eliminated under yearly peak and

monthly peak grid tariffs. The winter weekend profile particularly illustrates the comprehensive flexibility available, with high consumption periods under the volumetric grid tariff becoming substantially flattened and redistributed across different time periods under peak based structures.

Figure 4.22: Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS and EV

Figure 4.23: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS and EV

Photovoltaic (PV), battery energy storage systems (BESS), heat pumps (HPs) and electric vehicle (EV)

Households with the comprehensive combination of PV systems, BESS, EV, and HPs represent the most responsive technology configuration, as demonstrated in Figures 4.24 and 4.25. The annual consumption profile exhibits the most pronounced seasonal variation due to heat pump operation, while simultaneously showing the greatest differentiation between tariff structures. This comprehensive technology combination enables maximum load management capabilities through coordinated optimization of BESS, EV charging, and HP operation.

The seasonal profiles demonstrate the ultimate flexibility potential available through comprehensive technology integration. Summer weekday and weekend profiles show dramatic load redistribution capabilities, with volumetric grid tariff profiles displaying concentrated consumption peaks during early morning hours (00:00-06:00) and evening periods (21:00-24:00) that become substantially flattened under peak based grid tariffs. The summer profiles maintain relatively consistent consumption levels across peak-based structures, indicating effective load balancing through coordinated system operation. Winter profiles reveal the most extensive load shifting behav-

iors, with volumetric grid tariff profiles showing intense early morning consumption events (00:00-06:00) reaching above 0.012 MW that become virtually eliminated under yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariffs. The winter weekend profile particularly exemplifies comprehensive flexibility, with extremely high consumption periods under the volumetric grid tariff becoming dramatically redistributed and flattened under peak based structures.

Figure 4.24: Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS, HP, and EV

Figure 4.25: Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS, HP, and EV

4.2 Comparative analysis of scenario–tariff combinations

This section presents a comparative overview of the simulation results obtained in all scenario-grid tariff combinations, focusing on total household energy costs and system-level performance indicators. The analysis is structured to first examine the composition of total annual energy costs for all 60 modeled households. Subsequently, total electricity costs are disaggregated into their constituent components. To reflect how different grid tariff designs affect household-level outcomes, the analysis includes average values for electricity costs, grid tariff, and peak load demand throughout the sample. Finally, percentage changes in these key metrics are presented relative to the baseline volumetric grid tariff, providing a reference point for assessing the performance of alternative grid tariff structures in both future adoption scenarios.

4.2.1 Composition of total annual energy costs in all households

This subsection presents the total annual energy costs in each scenario–grid tariff combination. These costs include both electricity and gas expenditures. While electricity costs vary depending on the applied tariff structure and the level of technology adoption in each scenario, the gas price per megawatt-hour (MW) remains fixed in all simulations. However, total gas costs differ by household based on individual consumption patterns.

Figure 4.26 illustrates the composition of total annual energy costs in all households, depicting the constitution of electricity and gas under each combination of scenario-grid tariff. The corresponding numerical values are provided in Table 4.2. In the Stress-Test scenario, the higher adoption of electric technologies drives electricity costs above 70% of total energy spending, while in the BAU scenario, the share remains closer to 60%, reflecting a more balanced distribution. Together, these visual and quantitative comparisons show how technology adoption levels and grid tariff structures jointly influence the composition of household energy costs.

Figure 4.26: Breakdown of total annual household energy costs

Table 4.2: Total annual energy costs of all households

Scenario	Grid tariff type	Total energy costs (€/yr)	Gas costs (€/yr)	Electricity costs (€/yr)
BAU	Volumetric	130,281	49,590	80,691
	Yearly peak	124,401	49,590	74,811
	Monthly peak	124,495	49,590	74,904
Stress-Test	Volumetric	143190	34,792	108398
	Yearly peak	128,448	34,792	93,656
	Monthly peak	128,339	34,792	93,547

4.2.2 Total annual electricity expenditures by cost component

Figure 4.27 illustrates the composition of total electricity expenditures, disaggregated into energy price, grid tariff charges, and taxes and levies, in all combinations of scenario–grid tariff. The corresponding numerical values are provided in table 4.3. These results aggregate the annual electricity costs of all households, offering a comprehensive view of how cost structures vary.

Across both scenarios, a consistent decline in grid tariff charges is observed when transitioning from volumetric to peak-based grid tariffs, with the reduction being more substantial in the Stress-Test case. Although overall electricity demand is higher under Stress-Test conditions, the introduction of peak-based pricing leads to significantly lower grid-related expenditures.

Meanwhile, energy prices and taxes remain largely stable across all tariffs, reflecting their independence from the grid pricing structure.

Figure 4.27: Composition of total electricity costs

Table 4.3: Total annual electricity costs of all households

Scenario	Grid tariff type	Total electricity costs (€/yr)	Energy price (€/yr)	Grid tariff (€/yr)	Taxes & Levies (€/yr)
BAU	Volumetric	80,691	52,563	23,014	5,114
	Yearly peak	74,811	52,788	16,887	5,136
	Monthly peak	74,904	52,939	16,815	5,151
Stress-Test	Volumetric	108,398	70,611	30,916	6,870
	Yearly peak	93,656	71,217	15,510	6,929
	Monthly peak	93,547	71,530	15,058	6,960

4.2.3 Average household electricity cost, grid tariff charges, and peak load contribution

Figure 4.28 and Table 4.4 present the average annual electricity costs, grid tariff charges, and peak load contributions per household across all combinations of scenario–grid tariff. In contrast to the previous subsection, which examined total electricity costs aggregated across all households, this section offers an average per household to better highlight differences in individual cost and grid impacts.

The results confirm earlier trends: grid tariff charges and household peak loads both decrease significantly under peak-based pricing, with reductions most pronounced in the Stress-Test scenario. Despite the higher average electricity consumption in this scenario, applying peak tariffs still results in lower grid-related expenditures compared to the volumetric baseline. Overall electricity costs per household follow the same pattern, lowest under peak-based grid tariffs and highest under the volumetric design.

(a) Average annual electricity cost per household

(b) Average annual grid tariff per household

(c) Average annual peak load per household

Figure 4.28: Average annual costs and peak load per household

Table 4.4: Average annual costs and peak load per household

Scenario	Grid tariff type	Electricity cost (€/yr)	Grid tariff (€/yr)	Peak load (MW)
BAU	Volumetric	1,344.84	383.56	0.00783
	Yearly peak	1,246.85	281.45	0.00574
	Monthly peak	1,248.4	280.24	0.00575
Stress-Test	Volumetric	1,806.63	515.27	0.00992
	Yearly peak	1,560.93	258.49	0.00498
	Monthly peak	1,559.12	250.96	0.00498

4.2.4 Relative change in key metrics compared to the volumetric grid tariff baseline

Figure 4.29 and Table 4.5 present the relative changes in electricity costs, grid tariff charges, and peak load contributions under yearly and monthly peak based grid tariffs, using the volumetric tariff as a baseline. Results are disaggregated by scenario to capture how grid tariff impacts vary with the level of household electrification.

The outcomes align with trends identified in earlier sections: peak-based tariffs consistently outperform the volumetric design in all key metrics. Notably, their effectiveness is magnified in the Stress-Test scenario, where higher electrification levels lead to more pronounced reductions in both grid charges and peak load contributions.

By quantifying these relative shifts, the results highlight the growing value of demand-responsive tariff structures in managing costs and grid stress under future energy use patterns.

(a) BAU scenario

(b) Stress-Test scenario

Figure 4.29: Relative change in cost and peak load compared to Volumetric grid tariff

Table 4.5: Relative change in cost and peak load compared to Volumetric grid tariff

Scenario	Grid tariff type	Electricity cost (%)	Grid tariff (%)	Peak load (%)
BAU	Volumetric	0	0	0
	Yearly peak	-7.3	-26.6	-26.7
	Monthly peak	-7.2	-26.9	-26.6
Stress-Test	Volumetric	0	0	0
	Yearly peak	-13.6	-49.8	-49.8
	Monthly peak	-13.7	-51.3	-49.8

4.3 Detailed results by household flexibility category

4.3.1 Results by grid tariff type

This subsection examines the performance of different grid tariff structures across household flexibility categories, analyzing both the peak demand reduction potential and the associated grid tariff costs. The analysis compares the volumetric, yearly peak, and monthly peak grid tariffs for households with varying annual demand levels within each flexibility category. Results are presented for both the BAU and the Stress-Test scenarios to assess the robustness of grid tariff performance under different technology adoption conditions.

Very Flexible households

Figure 4.30 and Table 4.6 present the results for very flexible households equipped with a comprehensive portfolio of distributed generation and flexible household technologies. The analysis reveals distinct performance patterns across the three annual demand levels under different tariff structures.

For low annual demand household, peak demand remains relatively stable across all tariff types in both scenarios, maintaining approximately 0.006 MW. Grid tariff costs show minimal variation, ranging from €261-€307 in the BAU scenario and

€274-€422 in the Stress-Test scenario. The volumetric grid tariff yields the lowest costs for this demand category, suggesting that peak-based grid tariffs may not provide economic advantages to households with inherently low consumption patterns.

Medium annual demand household demonstrate the most pronounced responsiveness to tariff design changes. Peak demand exhibits substantial reduction from the volumetric grid tariff (0.014 MW in BAU, 0.018 MW in Stress-Test) to both peak based grid tariffs (approximately 0.004 MW across both scenarios). This reduction represents a decrease of approximately 70% in peak demand, indicating significant load-shifting capability. Correspondingly, grid tariff costs decrease dramatically from €884 (BAU) and €1,160 (Stress-Test) under the volumetric grid tariff to €210-€225 under peak based grid tariffs, demonstrating substantial economic benefits from grid tariff restructuring.

High annual demand household show the most significant peak demand reductions in absolute terms. Peak demand decreases from 0.027 MW under the volumetric tariff to approximately 0.004 MW under both yearly and monthly peak grid tariffs across both scenarios. This represents the largest absolute reduction among all demand categories, declining from over €2,000 annually under the volumetric grid tariff to approximately €220-€240 under peak based grid tariffs in both scenarios.

Figure 4.30: Impact of different grid tariffs on very flexible households

Table 4.6: Grid tariff comparison for Very flexible households

Scenario	BAU		Stress-Test	
	Peak demand (MW)	Grid tariff (€/year)	Peak demand (MW)	Grid tariff (€/year)
Volumetric	0.0058	307	0.0104	422
	0.0138	884	0.0183	1160
	0.0269	2,055	0.0269	2,055
Yearly peak	0.0058	282	0.0058	299
	0.0043	212	0.0043	225
	0.0043	210	0.0043	222
Monthly peak	0.0058	261	0.0058	274
	0.0043	172	0.0043	183
	0.0046	230	0.0046	236

Flexible households

Figure 4.31 and Table 4.7 present results for flexible households with partial distributed generation and flexible household technologies. These households exhibit markedly different response patterns compared to their very flexible counterparts, demonstrating limited peak reduction capabilities across all grid tariff structures.

Peak demand levels remain essentially unchanged across all grid tariff types for flexible households, with values hovering around 0.005 MW for low annual demand, 0.007 MW for medium annual demand, and 0.015 MW for high annual demand households in both scenarios. This stability indicates that households with limited flexibility resources cannot effectively respond to peak-based pricing signals through load shifting.

The economic implications differ significantly from very flexible households. For low and medium annual demand flexible households, peak-based grid tariffs result in higher grid costs compared to the volumetric baseline. Low demand household experience increases from €124 to €205-€229 (BAU) and €124 to €215-€243 (Stress-Test), while medium demand household see costs rise from €252 to €287-€340 (BAU) and €252 to €304-€360 (Stress-Test). This cost penalty reflects the inability of these households to reduce their peak consumption sufficiently to benefit from

the lower peak based rates.

High annual demand flexible household present a contrasting pattern, achieving modest cost reductions under peak-based tariffs despite minimal peak demand changes. Grid costs decrease from €747 to €287-€296 (BAU) and €747 to €304-€311 (Stress-Test), suggesting that even limited flexibility can provide economic benefits at higher consumption levels where the absolute impact of peak reduction is more significant.

Figure 4.31: Impact of different grid tariffs on flexible households

Table 4.7: Grid tariff comparison for Flexible households

Scenario	BAU		Stress-Test	
	Peak demand (MW)	Grid tariff (€/year)	Peak demand (MW)	Grid tariff (€/year)
Volumetric	0.0047	124	0.0047	124
	0.0069	252	0.0069	252
	0.0152	747	0.0152	747
Yearly peak	0.0047	229	0.0047	243
	0.0069	340	0.0069	360
	0.0059	287	0.0059	304
Monthly peak	0.0047	205	0.0047	215
	0.0069	334	0.0069	351
	0.0059	296	0.0059	311

Inflexible households

Figure 4.32 and Table 4.8 present results for inflexible households without distributed generation and flexible household technologies. These households demonstrate an intermediate response profile, exhibiting some peak reduction capability while facing mixed economic outcomes under peak-based tariffs.

Low and medium annual demand households show minimal peak demand variation across tariff types, maintaining levels around 0.003-0.004 MW and 0.007-0.008 MW respectively, in both scenarios. The economic impact follows a pattern similar to flexible households, with peak-based tariffs imposing cost penalties. Low demand household experience increases from €90 to €168-€192 (BAU) and €90 to €178-€202 (Stress-Test), while medium demand household see costs decrease from €415 to €359-€384 (BAU) and €415 to €380-€404 (Stress-Test).

High annual demand household exhibit notable peak reduction capabilities due to the presence of heat pumps for space and water heating, which provide some degree of thermal flexibility. Peak demand decreases from approximately 0.016 MW under the volumetric tariff to 0.011-0.012 MW under peak-based tariffs in both scenarios. This reduction translates to substantial cost savings, with grid tariff expenses declining from €1,085 to €582-€613 (BAU) and €1,085 to €617-€644

(Stress-Test). The thermal mass of buildings allows heat pumps to shift operation timing without compromising comfort, enabling meaningful peak reductions even in the absence of other distributed generation and flexible household technologies.

Figure 4.32: Impact of different grid tariffs on inflexible households

Table 4.8: Grid tariff comparison for Inflexible households

Scenario	BAU		Stress-Test	
	Peak demand (MW)	Grid tariff (€/year)	Peak demand (MW)	Grid tariff (€/year)
Volumetric	0.0034	90	0.0034	90
	0.0073	415	0.0073	415
	0.0160	1,085	0.0160	1,085
Yearly peak	0.0034	168	0.0034	178
	0.0073	359	0.0073	380
	0.0119	582	0.0119	617
Monthly peak	0.0034	192	0.0034	202
	0.0073	384	0.0073	404
	0.0119	613	0.0119	644

The results reveal distinct performance patterns across flexibility categories under different grid tariff structures. Very flexible households demonstrate superior peak reduction capabilities and achieve the greatest economic benefits from peak-based grid tariffs across all demand levels. Flexible households show limited responsiveness to grid tariff signals, with peak based grid tariffs generally imposing cost penalties except for high demand consumers. Inflexible households present an intermediate profile, achieving modest benefits primarily at high consumption levels through behavioral adaptations.

Both yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariffs demonstrate comparable effectiveness across all household categories, with minimal differences in peak demand levels or grid tariff costs. The consistency between BAU and Stress-Test scenarios indicates that grid tariff performance remains stable across different technology adoption contexts.

4.3.2 Results by technology combinations

This subsection examines the performance of specific distributed generation and flexible household technology combinations under different grid tariff structures. The analysis focuses on peak demand characteristics and grid tariff costs across eight distinct technology configurations, ranging from comprehensive multi-technology systems to households without any distributed technologies. Figure 4.33 and Table 4.9 present the comparative results across all grid tariff types. Figure 4.33 the primary Y-axis represents peak demand (MW), and the secondary Y-axis represents grid tariffs (€/year).

High flexibility technology combinations

Technology combinations incorporating multiple distributed energy resources demonstrate superior peak reduction capabilities under peak based grid tariffs. Both PV+BESS+EV+HP and PV+BESS+EV configurations achieve exceptional performance, representing the most effective technology combinations for grid management applications.

The PV+BESS+EV+HP configuration exhibits outstanding response capabilities, with peak demand decreasing from 0.018 MW under the volumetric tariff to approximately 0.003 MW under both yearly and monthly peak grid tariffs. This reduction of approximately 83% represents the highest relative peak reduction among all technology combinations. Grid tariff costs correspondingly decrease from €1,203 under the volumetric grid tariff to €147-€130 under peak based structures.

The PV+BESS+EV combination shows similarly robust performance, achieving peak demand reductions from 0.014 MW to approximately 0.001 MW in peak-based grid tariffs. Grid costs decrease from €694 to €69-€78, demonstrating substantial economic benefits. These comprehensive technology combinations leverage the complementary flexibility of battery storage, electric vehicle charging management, and thermal systems to achieve optimal peak shaving performance.

Medium flexibility technology combinations

Technology combinations with partially distributed energy resources exhibit moderate response to peak-based grid tariff signals. The PV+BESS configuration demonstrates a meaningful peak reduction from 0.008 MW to approximately 0.004 MW under peak based grid tariffs, with grid costs decreasing from €353 to €297-€265.

The presence of battery storage enables effective load shifting despite the absence of other flexible technologies.

PV+EV and PV+HP combinations show similar performance characteristics, maintaining peak demands around 0.007-0.011 MW in all grid tariff types with modest cost variations. The HP-only configuration demonstrates limited peak reduction capability, reflecting the constrained flexibility of thermal systems without complementary storage or generation resources.

Low flexibility technology combinations

Households with minimal distributed technologies exhibit limited response to changes in grid tariff design. The PV-only configuration maintains consistent peak demand levels around 0.008 MW across all grid tariff structures, with grid costs showing minimal variation from €383-€512. The absence of storage or flexible load technologies constrains the ability to shift consumption patterns in response to peak based pricing signals.

Households without any distributed technologies ("Non-technology") demonstrate the least flexibility, maintaining steady peak demands around 0.009 MW and experiencing modest cost increases under peak based grid tariffs from €499 to €445-€503, reflecting the inability to modify consumption behavior without technological support.

Figure 4.33: Peak demand and grid tariff analysis by technology

Table 4.9: Peak demand and grid tariff comparison across household technology configurations and tariff structures

Grid tariff type	Key metrics	PV+BESS +EV	PV+BESS +EV+HP	PV+BESS	PV+EV	HP	PV+HP	PV	No technology
Volumetric	Peak demand (MW)	0.01406	0.01824	0.00844	0.01404	0.01117	0.00950	0.00779	0.00859
Yearly peak		0.00134	0.00285	0.00404	0.00727	0.00656	0.00905	0.00779	0.00859
Monthly peak		0.00138	0.00285	0.00404	0.00727	0.00656	0.00905	0.00779	0.00859
Volumetric	Grid tariff (€/year)	694.91	1,203.35	353.40	637.85	858.58	530.48	383.65	499.02
Yearly peak		69.42	147.95	209.76	377.59	340.91	470.17	381.80	445.99
Monthly peak		78.65	129.56	205.71	382.36	365.43	512.98	414.66	493.84

The quantitative performance results correspond with the consumption pattern observations presented in Subsection 4.1.2. The load shifting behaviors observed in the representative profiles for PV+BESS+EV and PV+BESS+EV+HP households correspond to their quantitative performance, with peak demand reductions exceeding 80% in both configurations. The elimination of concentrated early morning consumption peaks (00:00-06:00) observed in these households' winter profiles under peak-based grid tariffs corresponds to their peak demand reductions.

The technology performance hierarchy reinforces the consumption pattern observations from Subsection 4.1.2. Households without distributed technologies or with PV systems alone, which showed minimal profile variation across grid tariff structures, show correspondingly limited quantitative improvements under peak based grid tariffs. The load shifting capabilities observed in heat pump systems correspond to measurable peak reduction potential, while combinations that incorporate BESS achieve substantial performance improvements that reflect their observed temporal arbitrage capabilities.

Multi-technology combinations that incorporate BESS, EV, and HPs have a higher peak reduction potential and economic benefits, corresponding to the comprehensive flexibility observed through coordinated system operation in Subsection 4.1.2. These households achieve optimal peak shaving performance under peak-based grid tariff structures.

BESS functions as a critical enabling technology, with combinations including BESS consistently outperforming their counterparts without storage capabilities. This finding corresponds to the substantial load management capabilities observed in storage system profiles, where high consumption periods were flattened and redistributed under peak based structures. Different flexibility resources provide complementary capabilities, as the combination of multiple technologies achieves a higher peak reduction than individual technology contributions.

The consistency of results between yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariffs across all technology combinations shows that the temporal granularity of peak measurement does not significantly influence household response capabilities. This finding suggests that yearly peak structures can achieve comparable grid management objectives while reducing administrative complexity for both distribution system operators and consumers.

The integration of consumption pattern analysis from Subsection 4.1.2 with quantitative performance metrics shows that observable load shifting behaviors in representative profiles correspond to technology effectiveness in grid management applications. Households exhibiting substantial consumption redistribution capabilities under peak-based grid tariffs consistently achieve superior peak demand reduction and grid tariff cost performance, establishing the role of distributed generation and flexible resources in enabling household participation in grid management initiatives.

4.4 Key findings summary

The simulation-based analysis that examines the economic effects for households of using grid tariffs to reduce peak demand in low-voltage grids reveals distinct patterns across tariff designs, household flexibility levels, and technology penetration scenarios. The results establish clear relationships between the configurations of household technology and the effectiveness of the tariff in achieving both economic benefits and peak demand reduction objectives.

Peak-based grid tariff structures consistently outperform volumetric designs in both economic and grid management metrics, with effectiveness amplified under higher technology adoption conditions. The Stress-Test scenario demonstrates improved responsiveness compared to the BAU scenario, indicating that increased electrification and the deployment of distributed technology create greater opportunities for tariff-based demand management. This pattern holds for all household categories and technology configurations examined in this study.

Household flexibility emerges as the primary determinant of tariff responsiveness, with very flexible households equipped with comprehensive technology combinations that achieve substantial economic benefits and peak reduction capabilities. The analysis establishes a clear technology hierarchy, where BESS function as critical enabling components for effective demand response. Multi-technology combinations that incorporate storage, electric vehicles, and heat pumps demonstrate superior performance compared to single-technology or non-technology configurations.

Economic outcomes vary considerably according to household characteristics, with benefits concentrated among households that have flexible technologies and higher annual demand levels. In contrast, households with limited flexibility experience mixed results under peak-based tariffs, indicating that the effectiveness of tariff design depends critically on the underlying capabilities and consumption patterns of household technology.

Consumption pattern analysis establishes direct correspondence between visual load shifting behaviors and quantitative performance outcomes. Households exhibiting substantial consumption redistribution capabilities achieve superior economic and peak reduction results, while those maintaining static consumption patterns show limited responsiveness to grid tariff signals. This relationship validates the connection between observable load management behaviors and measurable tariff effectiveness.

The yearly peak and monthly peak grid tariff structures achieve comparable performance across all metrics examined, suggesting that the temporal granularity of peak measurement does not significantly influence household response capabilities. This consistency occurs across all household categories and scenarios, indicating robust tariff design principles independent of specific peak measurement approaches.

In summary, the results reveal that peak based grid tariffs can effectively achieve the dual objectives of reducing household electricity costs and managing peak demand, the results determined primarily by household technology flexibility and adoption levels. These findings establish the basis for the evaluation of optimal tariff design strategies and implementation considerations in the following discussion section.

4.5 Integrated discussion and insights

4.5.1 Interpretation of key findings

Economic impacts across household types

The economic impacts reveal distinct patterns in the configurations of household technology, with very flexible households achieving substantial cost reductions while households with limited flexibility resources experience mixed results. High annual demand, very flexible households experience the most significant benefits, with grid tariff costs declining from €2,055 to €210–€240 under peak-based tariffs. This pattern is consistent with empirical modeling evidence that households endowed with flexibility technologies (especially storage) can reshuffle consumption to avoid capacity charges, while households without flexibility face limited scope to react to power-based signals [8, 11, 13]. In the Austrian context, recent end-customer test tariffs explicitly operationalize power or peak based network charges, reinforcing the mechanism observed here [7].

Peak-based grid tariffs under higher adoption

Peak-based grid tariffs demonstrate substantially greater effectiveness in the Stress-Test scenario compared to BAU, with average peak reductions of 49.8% versus 26.7%, respectively. The studies point in the same direction; when the share of electrified or flexible demand and DER increases, the ability of power or peak-based tariffs to lower contracted capacity and mitigate peaks increases. In a two-scenario evaluation with low versus high flexibility, monthly and yearly peak grid tariffs delivered the strongest reductions in capacity-related costs in the high flexibility case, and overall tariff performance explicitly differed with DER penetration; moreover, the authors note that enabling smart EV charging would further amplify the effect [11]. Regional system studies for Austria similarly show that electrification coupled with demand-side management increases technical headroom for shifting and peak relief, which is precisely what peak-based signals monetize [16].

Battery storage as the critical enabler

Battery energy storage systems emerge as the critical enabling technology for household flexibility, with all BESS-equipped configurations consistently outperforming their non-storage counterparts. Comparative analyses of residential tariff response

show that (i) under capacity/peak components, the battery is dispatched primarily to shave off-take peaks and therefore lower distribution-related charges, (ii) the presence of other flexible demand (e.g., heat pumps) increases the utilization and value of the battery, and (iii) households combining PV with storage and especially PV+EV+BESS achieve the largest tariff-driven benefits [8, 11]. This aligns with tariff design principles that target cost-driving peaks: technologies providing round-the-clock charge–discharge arbitrage directly address the power component, while unidirectional, time-shift-only options (e.g., scheduled EV charging without vehicle-to-home) or comfort-bounded thermal storage offer narrower flexibility windows [17].

4.5.2 Implications for key stakeholders

Households

The results indicate that the implementation of peak based tariffs creates pronounced economic differences among household types, with outcomes driven primarily by technology endowment and consumption patterns. Very flexible households with comprehensive technology combinations achieved the largest cost reductions, for the high annual demand households reducing grid tariff charges from €2,055 to €210–€240 under peak-based structures. This aligns with empirical findings from [9], who report that consumers equipped with photovoltaic (PV) systems, battery energy storage systems (BESS), and smart controls achieve disproportionate benefits under capacity-based network charges due to their ability to strategically reduce billed peak capacity. Similarly, [39] shows that capacity-oriented tariffs reward those with higher flexibility potential, while households with limited flexibility often face neutral or negative bill impacts.

In contrast, flexible and inflexible households in the simulations experienced grid tariff increases of €124–€243 in low-to-medium demand categories. This mirrors the distributional patterns identified by [9, 13], they find that households without enabling technologies are unable to sufficiently shift consumption away from peak periods, thereby incurring higher capacity charges. Such outcomes raise equity concerns, as the economic benefits of peak-based tariffs tend to concentrate among households with greater financial resources to invest in flexibility technologies [39]. These findings reinforce the importance of integrating distributional assessments into tariff design, a point emphasized in ACER’s (2025) review of European tariff reforms [38]. The review cautions that, without targeted measures, tariff shifts toward capacity-based structures may disproportionately burden lower income or technology-poor households.

Distribution System Operators (DSOs)

The thesis results show that under the widespread adoption of peak based grid tariffs, DSOs face significant revenue challenges, with Stress-Test scenario households reducing grid tariff charges by 49.8–51.3%. ACER (2025) describes this dynamic as a “vicious circle”: falling billed revenues due to consumer load shifting occur alongside increasing investment needs to integrate distributed resources and electrification, potentially lowering cost recovery unless tariff levels are periodically calibrated. The study [13] noted that network CAPEX is driven primarily by maximum coincident demand, not average utilization, which means that even substantial reductions in individual household peaks may not proportionally reduce DSO infrastructure costs.

Austrian-specific insights from [7] show that end-customer pilot tariffs, tested by Linz Netz and Energienetze Steiermark, incorporated daily quarter-hourly peak charges and defined capacity components to send strong load-reduction signals. While these pilots successfully reduced measured peaks for participating customers, they also highlight the revenue sufficiency challenge that if tariff levels remain fixed, successful peak reductions directly reduce billed capacity charges without offsetting fixed-cost recovery. The Austrian regulatory model, as described by [38], addresses this through an allowed revenue framework under the supervision of the E-Control, allowing adjustments to tariff levels in future periods to maintain revenue adequacy.

Operationally, peak-based tariffs can deliver system benefits by deferring reinforcement and reducing congestion, as evidenced by Slovenian and Spanish capacity based reforms summarized in [12, 38] which further stress that while dynamic peak oriented pricing is effective for managing congestion, its deployment must be paired with residual cost-recovery mechanisms to prevent underfunding essential network investments.

Policymakers

The dual challenge for policymakers is to preserve the efficiency incentives of peak-based tariffs while ensuring equitable cost distribution and sustainable DSO revenues. Current European regulatory practice, as codified by [38], holds that “all network users should contribute to network costs unless the non-payment of network charges is justified by system-beneficial impacts” (p. 28). This principle underscores the need to pair tariff reform with targeted support for consumers unable to invest in flexibility.

A study by [14] provides relevant best-practice examples from recent European energy market interventions, highlighting targeted subsidies, concessional financing

for enabling technologies, and transitional tariff designs that gradually introduce stronger capacity signals while mitigating regressive impacts. Such measures could be directly adapted to the Austrian context, where [7] pilot experience demonstrates the feasibility of operationalizing capacity-based charges in low-voltage networks.

From a regulatory design perspective, [17] emphasizes that revenue sufficiency and efficient pricing can be reconciled by separating marginal cost reflecting components from fixed or Ramsey-style residual charges. ACER (2025) [38] recommends benefit-based cost allocation for new investments, transparent residual cost recovery, and regular "fitness checks" of tariff methodologies to ensure efficiency and fairness outcomes do not erode with changing consumption patterns. Coordinated policy and regulatory adjustments will, therefore, be essential to avoid undue cost shifts between user groups while maintaining the peak reduction incentives demonstrated in our results.

4.5.3 Limitations and future research

Result limitations

Several limitations emerged from the analysis that constrain the generalizability and applicability of the findings. The optimization model assumes a perfect household response to pricing signals, which may not reflect real-world behavior where households make suboptimal decisions due to convenience, limited automation, or information constraints. Evidence from the response to residential demand shows a consistent gap between technically optimal scheduling and actual behavior, driven by comfort, usability, and attention limits [15, 40]. Consequently, the cost savings and peak reductions observed in this study should be interpreted as upper bound potentials for Stress-Test rather than expected realized outcomes.

The analysis focuses on individual household optimization without capturing system-wide feedback that may arise when many households respond to peak-based tariffs simultaneously. The substantial reductions in grid tariff charges reported for the Stress-Test scenario (49.8–51.3%) assume that tariff levels remain unchanged; in practice, regulatory re-calibration could alter outcomes for households and system operators.

Technology size limitations were apparent: photovoltaic capacities in several profiles were insufficient to fully cover demand during favorable generation windows, forcing continued grid imports despite available solar resources. This underscores

the importance of appropriate sizing and coordination of distributed generation and flexible household technologies to maximize tariff-related benefits.

Finally, the modeling is static with respect to technology cost trajectories, evolving consumption patterns, and learning effects; these dynamics could materially influence tariff effectiveness as markets and user capabilities evolve.

Future research

Future research should investigate the willingness of consumers to participate in peak-based grid tariff programs in specific regional contexts such as Upper Austria. Understanding adoption barriers, behavioral constraints, and acceptance factors would provide insight into realistic implementation potential and inform the design of effective policy support mechanisms. Recent studies on the acceptance of dynamic electricity pricing highlight the importance of sociodemographic factors, trust in utilities, and perceived control over consumption, suggesting that policy measures must address both economic and behavioral determinants of participation [16].

In addition, future work should address three practical avenues that follow directly from these results and the Austrian context. First, a technical assessment from the DSO perspective is needed to examine how widespread adoption of peak-based tariffs affects day-to-day operation, maintenance scheduling, and reinforcement planning; such analysis should quantify the trade-offs between reduced peak utilization and the persistent requirement to dimension assets for maximum coincident demand. Second, a rigorous household investment analysis should evaluate the financial attractiveness of different technology portfolios (e.g., PV, BESS, HPs, EV, and control/automation) under alternative tariff structures and price levels, identifying conditions under which specific bundles become cost-effective for distinct household types in Upper Austria. Third, the modeling framework should be extended to a wider set of tariff designs, including time-of-use variants, seasonal adjustments, and hybrid capacity–energy charges. It should explicitly embed feeder-level capacity limits and network topology to capture congestion formation and tariff-induced reallocation effects with greater realism.

5 Conclusion

This thesis examines how alternative grid tariff designs shape household electricity costs and peak demand at the low-voltage level in Austria. Using an optimization-based framework across two technology penetration scenarios and three tariff structures, the analysis shows that tariff design materially influences both economic outcomes for households and technical outcomes relevant to distribution networks. In particular, peak-based designs provide stronger incentives for peak reduction and can lower bills for households able to adapt their demand profile, while the volumetric baseline provides weaker signals for coincident demand management.

Using 15-minute data for 60 Austrian households and a linear optimization framework in two scenarios (BAU and Stress-Test), the study shows that peak-based tariffs reduce total household costs by approximately 7.2–7.3% in BAU and 13.6–13.7% in Stress-Test, driven by reductions in grid-tariff charges on the order of 26.6–26.9% (BAU) and 49.8–51.3% (Stress-Test). The average peak reductions are substantial, about 26.7% in BAU and 49.8% in Stress-Test, indicating that stronger adoption of flexible technologies amplifies the effectiveness of peak-aligned price signals. Battery energy storage emerges as the critical enabler of household flexibility: configurations with storage consistently outperform those without, while electric vehicles contribute through off-peak charging and heat pumps provide bounded thermal shifting. The distributional pattern is clear: very flexible, high-demand households capture the largest benefits (for example, grid-tariff charges falling from roughly €2,055 to €210–€240), whereas households with limited flexibility can face increases in the range of €124–€243 in low-to-medium demand categories.

Methodologically, the thesis contributes a structured comparison that links tariff design, household flexibility profiles, and peak metrics in an Austrian context. The scenario design and optimization approach enable scenario-controlled comparisons across tariff structures and technology configurations, revealing which combinations of design features and household capabilities are most likely to deliver economic savings alongside peak reduction. While the model intentionally assumes a perfect response within technical constraints to isolate tariff incentives and avoid confounding with behavioral heterogeneity, hence the resulting figures should be read as upper-bound potentials rather than forecasts of realized behavior. The household-level granularity and explicit treatment of technology portfolios address a documented gap in the Austrian evidence base by quantifying distributional effects and clarify-

ing the mechanisms behind them, in particular, the role of shaving 15-minute import peaks that determine capacity-linked charges.

The broader implications are twofold. First, for households, tariff reform can unlock meaningful savings when paired with enabling technologies and basic automation (for example, timer-based EV charging or simple HEMS rules). In the absence of such capabilities, the same reform may shift costs toward users who are less able to respond, raising equity concerns that require attention in policy design. Second, for DSOs, the widespread success of peak-based incentives does not automatically translate into proportionate reductions in network investment needs because asset sizing is driven by maximum coincident demand at feeder/area level and reliability constraints. This underscores the need for stable, rule-based revenue-recovery arrangements (for example, periodic calibration of residual fixed/capacity components to maintain allowed revenue) that maintain cost sufficiency while preserving efficiency signals.

These findings suggest several practical recommendations. Tariff methodologies that place greater weight on capacity or peak-aligned components are more likely to target the cost drivers of low-voltage networks but are best implemented with safeguards to protect consumers with limited access to flexibility technologies. Targeted, time-bound support for battery storage and entry-level control systems, phased transition paths to mitigate transitory bill shocks, and clear communication of price signals can improve both effectiveness and fairness. On the regulatory side, functionally separating marginal signal components (time- and peak-based charges) from residual cost-recovery elements (fixed or capacity subscriptions set *ex ante*) helps maintain revenue stability as load shapes evolve, reducing the risk that a successful demand response undermines network financing.

The thesis contributes to the literature by (i) providing quantified, household-level evidence on how specific tariff designs interact with distinct technology portfolios in Austria; (ii) demonstrating that battery energy storage is a critical lever for aligning private incentives with system objectives; and (iii) translating model insights into policy-relevant design principles that reconcile peak management with equity and revenue sufficiency. Together, these contributions clarify where tariff reform is most promising, where it risks unintended redistribution, and how implementation choices can mitigate those risks.

Future work builds on these results along two near-term extensions and one longer-term line. Near-term empirical research on consumer acceptance and real-world responsiveness in Upper Austria is needed to calibrate the attainable share of the

modeled potential and to tailor support instruments. Near-term analytically, extending the modeling to include feeder-level constraints and a wider set of tariff variants would capture congestion formation and tariff-induced reallocation with greater realism. As a longer-term line, investment analyses at the household level should map the conditions under which different technology bundles become cost-effective for distinct user segments under alternative tariff levels and signal designs.

In summary, this thesis shows that grid tariff design is a powerful near-term lever to shape household costs and peak demand in Austria's low-voltage networks. When paired with pragmatic equity measures and robust cost recovery arrangements, well-calibrated, peak-aligned tariffs support a more flexible, affordable, and grid-efficient electrification pathway.

6 List of figures

3.1	Optimization workflow using IESopt [29]	23
3.2	Household energy system with integrated cost minimization under grid tariffs.	30
4.1	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Very flexible low demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff . .	35
4.2	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Very flexible medium demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff	36
4.3	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Very flexible high demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff . .	37
4.4	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Flexible low demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff	38
4.5	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Flexible medium demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff . .	39
4.6	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Flexible high demand household under different grid tariff structures:(a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff	40
4.7	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Inflexible low demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff	41
4.8	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Inflexible medium demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff . .	42
4.9	Electricity grid consumption patterns for Inflexible high demand household under different grid tariff structures: (a) volumetric grid tariff, (b) yearly grid peak tariff, and (c) monthly grid peak tariff	43
4.10	Annual power consumption analysis for household with no technology	45
4.11	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with no technology	46
4.12	Annual power consumption analysis for household with only PV . . .	47

4.13	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with only PV . . .	48
4.14	Annual power consumption analysis for household with only HPs . . .	49
4.15	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with only HPs . . .	50
4.16	Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV and HPs .	51
4.17	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with photovoltaic and HPs	52
4.18	Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV and BESS	53
4.19	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV and BESS	54
4.20	Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV and EV .	55
4.21	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV and EV	56
4.22	Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS and EV	57
4.23	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS and EV	58
4.24	Annual power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS, HP, and EV	59
4.25	Seasonal power consumption analysis for household with PV, BESS, HP, and EV	60
4.26	Breakdown of total annual household energy costs	62
4.27	Composition of total electricity costs	64
4.28	Average annual costs and peak load per household	66
4.29	Relative change in cost and peak load compared to Volumetric grid tariff	68
4.30	Impact of different grid tariffs on very flexible households	71
4.31	Impact of different grid tariffs on flexible households	74
4.32	Impact of different grid tariffs on inflexible households	76
4.33	Peak demand and grid tariff analysis by technology	80

7 List of tables

2.1	Grid levels and rated voltages in Austria [6]	7
3.1	Prices used in total cost calculation (including 20% VAT)	22
3.2	Economic and tariff-related model parameters.	25
3.3	Technical system parameters.	26
3.4	Number of households assigned each technology under the two scenarios	31
4.1	Calculated grid tariff values	33
4.2	Total annual energy costs of all households	63
4.3	Total annual electricity costs of all households	65
4.4	Average annual costs and peak load per household	67
4.5	Relative change in cost and peak load compared to Volumetric grid tariff	69
4.6	Grid tariff comparison for Very flexible households	72
4.7	Grid tariff comparison for Flexible households	75
4.8	Grid tariff comparison for Inflexible households	77
4.9	Peak demand and grid tariff comparison across household technology configurations and tariff structures	81
9.1	2030 PV scenario calculations for Upper Austria (UA)	99
9.2	2023 baseline calculation of residential battery storage attachment in Austria (AT)	99
9.3	2023 baseline calculation of residential battery storage attachment in UA	99
9.4	2030 battery storage scenario calculations for UA based on PV house- hold projections and attachment ratios	99
9.5	2030 heat pump scenario calculations for UA	99
9.6	2030 battery electric vehicle scenario calculations for UA	99

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9 Appendix

Table 9.1: 2030 PV scenario calculations for Upper Austria (UA)

Scenario	Total Cap. (GW)	Rooftop %	Rooftop Cap. (GW)	Sys. Size (kW)	PV HHs (mil)	% of HHs	PV HHs in 60
BAU	3.5	70%	2.4	7.5	0.32	45%	27
Stress-Test	4.5	70%	3.15	7.5	0.42	60%	36

Table 9.2: 2023 baseline calculation of residential battery storage attachment in Austria (AT)

Year	PV + BESS homes	PV homes	Attachment ratio
2023	94,136	857,142	10%

Table 9.3: 2023 baseline calculation of residential battery storage attachment in UA

Year	PV + BESS homes	PV homes	Attachment ratio
2023	14,120	128,333	11%

Table 9.4: 2030 battery storage scenario calculations for UA based on PV household projections and attachment ratios

Scenario	PV HHs (mil)	Attachment Ratio	Battery Homes	% of HHs	BESS HHs in 60
BAU	0.32	25%	0.08	11%	7
Stress-Test	0.42	50%	0.21	30%	18

Table 9.5: 2030 heat pump scenario calculations for UA

Scenario	2030 AT HP Stock	2030 UA HP Stock	% of HHs	HP HHs in 60
BAU	456,000	75,240	11%	7
Stress-Test	1,248,000	205,920	30%	18

Table 9.6: 2030 battery electric vehicle scenario calculations for UA

Scenario	2030 AT BEV Stock	2030 UA BEV Stock	% of HHs	EV HHs in 60
BAU (Statista)	505,870	83,468	12%	7
Stress-Test	1,264,674	208,671	30%	18